

Developing a Scale for Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital: A Multi-Dimensional Framework for Sustainable Performance in Pakistan's Manufacturing SMEs

¹Dr. Tarique Mahmood

Associate Professor, Management Studies Department, Bahria University Karachi, Pakistan.

Email: dr.tariquerana@gmail.com

²Dr. Muhammad Imran

Associate Professor, Business Studies Department, Bahria University Karachi, Pakistan.

Email: drsheikhmuhammadimran@gmail.com

³Dr. Liaqat Ali

Professor, Management Studies Department, Bahria University Karachi, Pakistan.

Email: 786liaqat@gmail.com

⁴Dr. Khawar Hussain

Assistant Professor, Business Studies Department, Bahria University Karachi, Pakistan.

Email: kharwaredu@yahoo.com

⁵Atif Nazeer Awan

Senior Lecturer, Business Studies Department, Bahria University Karachi, Pakistan.

Email: atifnazeer.awan@gmail.com

Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the role of ambidextrous intellectual capital (AIC) in the sustainable performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in Pakistan's manufacturing sector. This research employed meta-analysis and SmartPLS, PLS-SEM for data analysis. The results found AIC affects sustainable organizational performance through AO. When the analysis was undertaken for different industrial sectors, results showed AIC to be useful for all SMEs. Yet, the results were more promising for medium-sized enterprises compared to small ones. Accordingly, policy formulation at both the macro and micro levels should consider the dimensions and sub-dimensions of AIC, rather than just the AIC dimensions collectively.

Keywords- Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital, SME Sustainable Performance and Ambidextrous Organization

Introduction

Pakistan is aiming at achieving the status of the twenty-fifth largest economy in 2025 but the country is currently facing a turbulent economic climate that is evidenced by declining exports (Sucena, Matos, & Nunes, 2025). The manufacturing industry, which is important in foreign trade is

performing fluctuating; some of the companies have recorded significant progress but the industry is performing dismally overall in the last ten years (Nurseha, Afif, & Anwar, 2024). An attempt to improve the competence of firms has not been sufficient and intellectual capital (IC) remains a topic that has been left untouched by the policymakers and researchers. IC, i.e. structural capital (SC), human capital (HC) and relational capital (RC), is a core of organizational value creation and competitive advantage (Q. B. Ali, Zin, & bin Ismail, 2024). In addition, the principle of ambidexterity, which involves the need to put a balance between the exploratory and exploitative processes, is needed in order to use IC to achieve sustainable gains and enhance organizational performance (Chatterji & Kiran, 2023).

The issue that businesses face due to disruptive technologies and increased competition in the market is that, it changes the locus of the competitiveness to intangible, as opposed to tangible resources (Yang, Luo, & Pan, 2024). Resource-based view assumes that competitive advantage is based on resources that meet the VRIN requirements (valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable) (Dinu, Vătămănescu, Stăneiu, & Rusu, 2023). The intangible assets, including human capital and IC cannot be ignored in strategic formulation (Caputo, 2024). The best resources must add value to the business goals, be limited to maintain competitive advantage, imitable, and inimitable (Rehman, Ashfaq, Bresciani, Giacosa, & Mueller, 2023). The value creation of knowledge management and exchange is essential, as it has a more significant impact on the productivity of a firm than on tangible assets (Cosa, Pedro, & Urban, 2024). Some of the most important interdependent attributes in the economics of knowledge are globalization, computerization, economic disintermediation and the very nature of such resources being intangible (Abdallah, Amin, Abdelghany, & Elamer, 2025).

In the context of competitive advantage, IC plays a determining role, as it determines the organizational modes of organization of exploitative and exploration activities (Lopez-Zapata & Ramírez-Gómez, 2023). HC, RC, and SC are interrelated in terms of various organizational levels and, thus, allow developing ambidextrous capabilities and enhance organizational performance (Taha, Siam, Alshurafat, & Al Shbail, 2024). The dissertation argues that organizational ambidexterity (OA) is a result of external knowledge management ability of an organization and that its impact in the IC-performance nexus has not been adequately studied (Huma, Muslim, & Ahmed, 2024). The research proposes the notion of ambidextrous intellectual capital (AIC) which is a set of knowledge and the ability to innovate that is needed to develop both the exploratory and exploitative processes. This research aims at incorporating IC variables, exploring AIC in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and examining the association between OA, IC, and organizational performance in Pakistan and thus adding a significant value to the available literature.

To achieve the ambidexterity, the organizations should formulate an AIC that would enable exploration and exploitation simultaneously (Asiaei, O'Connor, Barani, & Joshi, 2023). However, the available body of literature has so far only theorized the concept of ambidexterity as a strategic orientation but not as a capability (Ortiz-Regalado & Guevara, 2024). The achievement of ambidexterity requires planned developmental efforts, which in its turn brings the question of what aspects of AIC are central in achieving OA (Mahmood, Ali, Imran, Saleem, & Taous, 2025). Strict definition and measurement of AIC is thus unavoidable towards assessing its impact to performance

(Pak, Heidarian Ghaleh, & Mehralian, 2023). OA is closely tied to the improvement of the organizational capabilities, and a lack of productivity and innovation is one of the challenges that Pakistani SMEs face (Government of Pakistan, 2016-2018) (Shehzad, Zhang, Dost, Ahmad, & Alam, 2023). Enhancement of the organizational capabilities may help SMEs to attain ambidexterity and enhance performance but there is limited literature on the impact of AIC on firm performance through OA (Hassan, Raza, Malik, Ishaque, & Fiza, 2023). The current research, hence, aims at defining AIC, operationalizing it, and analyzing its effects on firm performances as per the growth agenda that the Pakistani government has on SMEs.

The literature review shows that there are gaps in research and unexplored areas that can be explored through scholarly research. Of particular relevance is the fact that very little research has been done on the topic of ambidexterity in organizations displaying a multi-domain and multilevel structure. SME manufacturing setting is an interesting research opportunity. The next chapter is the synthesis of literature and theoretical perspectives in the existing field to show that the holistic comprehension of the AIC construct is yet to be developed. Theoretical gaps here remain in the manner in which complex organizational structures may embody ambidexterity and the micro-processes in which they may be associated with are relatively poorly understood. Even though the advantages of AIC are supported by empirical evidence, the literature fails to describe the practical mechanisms and managerial practices that can bring this capability into existence. Although the majority of the empirical studies were conducted at the organizational or structural levels, comparatively little research has been done on the complex administrative role and the social environment within which it functions. The manufacturing sector plays an important role in any country's economy through its knowledge-based activities. This investigation is fundamentally about Pakistan, particularly SMEs in its manufacturing sector.

Literature Review and Theoretical Exposition

Human Capital Theory (HCT)

(Becker, 1962; Lewis, 1954) started his research work to create economics and then built the concept of human capital in his study, Economic development with unlimited supply of labor. Further advancement of this was made by Enke (1962) who said that investments in human capital (HC) is no longer the same negative thinking as before, but an established economic asset has come into existence (Auerbach & Green, 2024). Those who established the theoretical foundation include scholars such as Lewis, Becker and Mincer who associated human capital with the economic growth and distribution of income (Aslam, Mudassir, Ghouse, & Farooq, 2024). Investment in HC is considered essential with material capital as it improves individual and organizational productivity. According to studies by Alfalih (2023), there is a correlation between the HC distribution, technology, and economic progress and polarizing impacts of the varying home environment and foreign impacts. Rafid (2023) emphasizes that HC investments provide higher economic returns in the long-run in comparison with consumption costs (MATAACHE, 2023). Different educational researchers also make their contributions to the HC value, and one of the aspects is the significance of both formal and

informal education (Grugulis, 2024). HC contribution goes beyond the economic aspect to other sectors such as welfare and social equity towards supporting societal development by promoting a better education and resource use (Edeji, 2024). Individual capabilities and organizational management interplay lead to competitive advantages, and it is possible to say that human capabilities form an essential type of capital (England & Folbre, 2023).

Social Exchange Theory (SET)

The social exchange theory introduced by Bale (1981) is very important in explaining the workplace behavior in terms of mutual dependence and psychological norms of satiation. According to Lawler and Yoon (1998), the motivation behind behavior is the need to maximize on gains and minimize losses. Additionally, one of the most important contributions is the relationship between leaders and the teams, where in-group members tend to perform more than the job requirements (Ahmad, Nawaz, Ishaq, Khan, & Ashraf, 2023). Furthermore, quality leader-member interaction leads to increased productivity, satisfaction, and commitment and less role conflict. In addition, Wang, Hu, Park, Yuan, and Chen (2023) highlights the connection between the human resource management and the flexibility of employees, as well as the idea of conceptualizing the collective social exchange theory by Kilroy, Dundon, and Townsend (2023), which involves both the top-down and bottom-up processes in the social interactions within an organization. Moreover, social effects among the colleagues influence perceptions and reactions leading to a common sense of exchange relations in the workplace (Zhao & Detlor, 2023).

Resource-Based View (RBV)

Under the exploration of the resource-based view (RBV), it has been known that resources; tangible and intangible are part of the competitive advantage of an organization (Kero & Bogale, 2023). According to the RBV, performance and ability to innovate is determined by the strategic positioning of an organization which is dependent on the strengths and weaknesses of the organization (Kaur & Kumar, 2024). The human resources strategies are critical in developing distinctive capabilities that help in boosting the engagement and effectiveness of employees (Chen, Guo, & Huang, 2024). The capability lifecycle model represents the phases of the organizational capabilities development: founding, development and maturity, emphasizing the need to develop a systematic process of the utilization of resources as a competitive advantage that can be sustained (Civelek, Krajčák, & Ključnikov, 2023). Moreover, SMEs find it difficult in their expansion strategies to venture into the global markets, but considering the resource-based and the market-based perspectives can help them to enhance their export performance (El Nemar, El-Chaarani, Dandachi, & Castellano, 2025). In general, the effectiveness of mobilizing and managing organizational resources and capabilities is the key to the successful operation of an organization in performing competitive advantages under different conditions in the market (Abid, Dowling, Ceci, & Aftab, 2023).

Human Capital (HC)

HC is recognized in the literature as a key source of competitive advantage that is an excellent contributor to organizational performance. Although there does not exist a standardized definition of HC, it incorporates the experience, knowledge, skills, and abilities of the employees. It was Becker (1962) who first examined HC on the macro-level, which shifted to the dynamics of a firm in the 1990s and involved qualitative (attitude and motivation) and quantitative (education) elements (Abbas, Ekowati, Suhariadi, & Anwar, 2024). According to the research, HC deals with attitudes, knowledge and skills that are important to the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage, originating the concept of HC in the theories of economics introduced (Serenko, 2024). Becker also stressed that training and knowledge improvement of HC had an impact on firm performance whereas the research carried out in the early 90s defined such variables as creativity and problem-solving to be part of HC (Costa, Pádua, & Moreira, 2023). Organizational HC is the aggregate of skills that are possessed by employees, making it easy to react to problems and opportunities (Campanella, Serino, Battisti, Giakoumelou, & Karasamani, 2023). HC is also defined as the combination of knowledge and skills which is the economic value of the workforce expertise (Dimand, Abutabenjeh, Rodriguez-Plesa, Alkadry, & Bruns Ali, 2023). In addition, HC is a major aspect in improving the performance of firms and generating economic growth especially in developing countries (Vasilev, Stefanova, & Popescu, 2023). The main features of HC are creativity, knowledge, experience, capacity to work in a team, and innovativeness and learning ability (Rajput et al., 2023).

Structural Capital (SC)

SC refers to the systems and development that facilitate the business transactions of the employees. It is the knowledge that has been built up by an organization, incorporating a strategy, leadership practices, standard operating procedures, organizational culture, business processes, management styles, and supportive infrastructure (Vătămănescu, Bratianu, Dabija, & Popa, 2023). Yang et al. (2024) define organizational or process capital as intellectual property, to management philosophies, and management information systems, which are obtained due to the outputs of the organization over time. Nevertheless, most organizations underestimate the human resource, which is composed of skilled personnel, innovative ideas and work experience. Lack of SC is a big constraint to the ability of an organization to come up with ideas (Bananuka, Tauringana, & Tumwebaze, 2023). The SC is considered these days to be a set of human and organizational resources aimed at profit (Mukaro, Deka, & Rukani, 2023). Moreover, it consists of direct support, the physical items that are touched by the employees like desks and computers, and implicit support that encompasses software, information systems, marketing plans, and business know-how (Sarwar & Mustafa, 2024). Also, under indirect support there is the necessary infrastructure such as buildings and utilities as well as payroll systems and strategic plans (Rahma, Nurcahyono, Sinarasri, & Ifada, 2023). Finally, SC enables such aspects as databases, research, and development, trademarks and innovation with the purpose to improve the performance of employees (Hina et al., 2024).

Relational Capital (RC)

Lee, Yeh, Yu, and Luo (2023) emphasize that a considerable number of satisfied customers is the key to organizational success and economic growth. RC is centered on customer relationship and marketing knowledge, and without these companies cannot compete better than those of their rivals (Chatterji & Kiran, 2023). Most managers do not realize the importance of the knowledge and wishes of their customers, and thus it can be a threat to the potential of the organization (Pant, Dutta, & Sarmah, 2024). RC is the intangible assets that are based on relations with suppliers, customers, industries and government bodies. Managers do not understand their customers, and this may result in dissatisfaction (Lopez-Zapata & Ramírez-Gómez, 2023). The RC, which is composed of internal and external relations of an organization is also regarded as an essential intangible asset that may be an asset or liability, depending on the stakeholder management (Q. B. Ali et al., 2024). Distribution relationships, customer interactions and satisfaction are also important elements of RC that can be used to achieve a competitive advantage on the contemporary knowledge economy (Saputra & Pratomo, 2023).

Ambidextrous organization (AO)

The ambidextrous structure is essential to survive in the current dynamic world where innovation and agility are the main priorities to stability and competitive edge (Hwang, Lai, & Wang, 2023). The dynamic competencies and strategic renewal are created by continuous learning and strategic renewal is increased by ambidexterity which increases the scope of strategic choice (Mulyana, Rusu, & Perjons, 2024). Organizational success relies on balancing between exploration and exploitation, as mentioned by (Rosing & Zacher, 2023). According to Pertheban et al. (2023), there are three balancing techniques, namely, structural ambidexterity, contextual ambidexterity, and temporal cycling (Ding, Li, Yang, & Xiao, 2023). This paper places on all organizational ambidexterity, in which the individual members are found to have dual capacities, which augments the organizational adaptability and cost-efficiency (Restuputri, Masudin, Septira, Govindan, & Widayat, 2024). Organizations however encounter the issue of deciding how to explore or exploit and both should be in line with organizational objectives to realize ambidextrous learning (Beh, 2023). Organizations need to compromise among the current feasibility and the prospective exploration. The meeting of the ambidexterity and economic crisis is still not completely addressed, implying that there is a necessity of the new directions of research in the organizational theory (Kafetzopoulos, Psomas, & Katou, 2023).

Organizational Ambidexterity Dimensions

The existing literature has emphasized several conceptualizations on the formation of the ambidextrous organization. The most prevalent kinds of AO are characterized into contextual, structural, innovative, and sequential ambidexterity:

Contextual Ambidexterity

Gibson and Birkinshaw (2004) originally coined the word contextual ambidexterity and denoted it as the interactive and behavioral capability to instantaneously determine adaptability and alignment. In

the interim, the alignment embraces steadiness amid the deeds of organizational functions and units (Tang & Wei, 2024). Concurrently, adaptability is interconnected to the ability to configure the organizational activities quickly in the association through changes in the organizational task (Rafik, 2023).

Innovative Ambidexterity

Innovative ambidexterity is considered an ambidextrous result indicator that detentions an organization's "exploration and exploitation" performance (Simsek, 2009). Innovative ambidexterity reveals the development of dis-continuous (exploratory) and incremental (exploitative) innovations together (Rafik, 2023).

Structural Ambidexterity

Structural separation integrates mechanisms across the "mono-dexterous" explorative and exploitative trade units. AO achieve and manage short-term and long-term growth and proficiency by the structural Ambidexterity of "exploration and exploitation" in different MNCs and SMEs (Tushman & O'Reilly III, 1996). It is grounded on the spatial parting of organizational divisions, which are equipped with ironic activities. In this regard, Stoiber, Matzler, and Hautz (2023) referred to it as empowering the mechanism of structural variation to fragment the organization system into sub-units. Each sub-unit inclines to create specific qualities aligned with the external environment and a suitable avenue for the organization's ambidexterity (Friedrich, 2023).

Sequential Ambidexterity

Sequential ambidexterity needs organizations to adapt elements of organization and architecture in line with exploration and exploitation. Thus, sequential ambidexterity has a transformational ability that permits organizations to adjust between exploratory and exploitative tasks and an implementing competency that caters to an appropriate organizational context to best utilize it in every period (Sun, Rong, Sun, & Zhu, 2023). It also implies a conceivable avenue to successfully maintain paradoxical activities. It provides an understanding of how organizations can become ambidextrous over time. Sequential ambidexterity can help to define the organization's ambidexterity (Rafik, 2023).

Hypothesis Development

Ambidextrous Intellectual capital (AIC) influence on Organizational Performance (OP):

Ambidextrous Human capital and Organizational Performance

The initial route of ambidexterity brought about by the personal HC is crucial towards the enhancement of innovation and knowledge. Organizational competencies cannot be developed without the development of ambidextrous HC that is a basic component (Pak et al., 2023). Ambidextrous HC comprises the skills, knowledge, behaviors, and abilities that allow one to think exploratory or exploitative, unlike the traditional HC strategies (Asiaei, O'Connor, et al., 2023). Another division of HC is suggested, depending on the distinction between specialists and generalists that underlies the different character of exploration and exploitation actions (Jyoti & Choudhary,

2024). Generalist HC incorporates employees who possess greater exploitative and explorative competencies which enable them to complete tasks efficiently through combination of the two actions (Siddiqui, Anwer, John, & Rabie, 2024). This type of HC is defined by the flexible capabilities, multi-skilled attitudes and diverse mental models, which make individuals be able to adapt, discover, understand, apply and interpret new knowledge (Huma et al., 2024). As a result, these versatile individuals are able to impactful exploit and explore as the explicit knowledge can be used down the line (Taha et al., 2024).

Specialist Human Capital

Organizations that establish human capital intend to build the knowledge distributed in nature where individuals have an overlapping knowledge structure.

Generalist Human Capital

Hence, the main issue of generalist human capital is to expand and preserve such behaviors of entrepreneurship for the exploration of knowledge and form a countervailing instrument to enable specific knowledge refined and integrated in an effective way, such as exploitation.

H1: Ambidextrous Human capital (AHC) has a positive influence on Organizational Performance (OP).

Ambidextrous Relational Capital and Organizational Performance

It is organizational ambidexterity that depends on both the internal and external relational capital (RC) which improves the performance of an organization. It implies that the work of generalists cannot be ambidextrous without a proper management of specialists (Yang et al., 2024). The integration of explorative and exploitative employees can enable organizations to develop ambidextrous groups by developing strong relational capital, which would support knowledge sharing (Huma et al., 2024). RC has cooperative (exploitation-oriented) and entrepreneurial (exploration-oriented) types, both of which need strong networks to be able to implement both approaches at the same time (Taha et al., 2024). Effective ambidexterity requires an effective relational structure, which enhances the incorporation of expertise of specialists, which is essential in innovation (Mahmood et al., 2025). Thus, it is necessary that organizations should have the capability of creating relational capital that is balanced in terms of exploration and exploitation that facilitates optimal functioning in ambidexterity (Ortiz-Regalado & Guevara, 2024).

Cooperative Relational Capital

Originally (Reagans & Zuckerman, 2001; Rulke & Galaskiewicz, 2000) found that cooperative relational capital enhances specialists' abilities to mobilize and search for the knowledge of others effectively under the structures of distributed knowledge. This enhancement is possible due to three reasons: affective, structural, and cognitive which supports these authorities assist, refine, and share particular knowledge for deep exploitation (Mohammad Shafiee, Warkentin, & Motamed, 2024).

Entrepreneurial Relational Capital

It provides variation and reaches the requirements to acquire new knowledge in diverse areas. Paoloni, De Andreis, and Papa (2024) suggested that individual personalities that are flexible to various social circumstances not only disperse social relationships but also influence network opportunities strategically.

H2: Ambidextrous Relational capital has a positive influence on Organizational Performance.

Ambidextrous Structural Capital and Organizational Performance

The document discusses the role of structural capital (SC) at the organizational level in fostering ambidexterity through the interplay of exploration and exploitation (Effendi, So, Setiadi, & Soepriyanto, 2024). It highlights that structural capital, comprising norms, structures, processes, and routines, is vital for facilitating interaction among organizational units, which enables the creation of new knowledge (Ortiz-Regalado & Guevara, 2024). However, rigid policies and existing routines may hinder an organization's capacity to be ambidextrous. The text distinguishes between mechanistic and organic structural capital, noting that mechanistic SC fosters exploitation while potentially inhibiting exploration (Martínez-Falcó, Marco-Lajara, Zaragoza-Sáez, & Sánchez-García, 2024), whereas organic SC is characterized by flexibility and less reliance on rigid procedures. The relationship between these forms of SC and their impact on organizational practices remains a topic of ongoing research (Melly & Mosong, 2024).

Organic Structural Capital

Organic structural capital provides flexibility and is more conducive to the ambidextrous organizational learning and acquisition essential for exploratory learning. Organic structural capital provides less controlled structures and enables individuals to be more flexible in acquiring new knowledge and modification in existing knowledge.

Mechanistic Structural Capital

Mechanistic SC can provide efficiency, integration, and stability, which are essential for exploitation while providing discretion and latitude required for exploration (Mahmood & Mubarik, 2020).

H3: Ambidextrous Structural capital has a positive influence on Organizational Performance.

Figure 1: Ambidexterity Model
Source: Mahmood and Mubarik (2020)

Mediating Ambidextrous Organization in AIC and Firm Performance

Ambidexterity within organizations fosters a supportive context enabling individuals to balance exploitation and exploration activities (Asiaei, Bontis, Askari, Yaghoubi, & Barani, 2023). Temporal ambidexterity, conceptualized through punctuated equilibrium, recommends alternating long-term exploration with short-term exploitation (Asiaei, O'Connor, et al., 2023). Research highlights the important links between exploration and exploitation in business units and leadership. Structural and temporal separation are strategies to navigate the inherent conflicts between these activities, while paradox management literature offers insights on handling organizational paradoxes (Shehzad et al., 2023). Exploration and exploitation are defined by (Taha et al., 2024) as opposing learning methods, necessitating ambidexterity to manage the tensions they create. Contextual ambidexterity, noted by Hayaeian and Hesarzadeh (2024), accepts balancing these activities within a single organization, emphasizing individual capabilities to effectively divide time between them. The ongoing conflict about maintaining balance between exploration and exploitation remains unresolved, as indicated by Hassan et al. (2023). The paradox framework aids in understanding the underlying tensions and defenses actors exhibit in addressing these paradoxes. Successful ambidextrous organizations often depend on leaders' dynamic decision-making and commitment to overarching visions. Knowledge creation, a crucial area largely overlooked in management research, is highlighted by Zahid, Zhang, Shahzad, Junaid, and Shrivastava (2024) as vital for global competitiveness, necessitating strategies for managing knowledge-related intangible assets (Elmakkawy, Hassan, & Magdy, 2025). The transition from manufacturing to a service-oriented economy accentuates the need for organizations to innovate their knowledge assets continuously. The concept of Continuous Organizational Ambidexterity is essential for effective international business strategies (Khalequzzaman, Wang, Zhang, & Wang, 2025). Organizations unable to leverage their knowledge face survival challenges. Attention to Ambidexterity-Intensified Companies is necessary, especially for those reliant on knowledge-heavy services and innovation (Xi, Fang, Feng, & Liu, 2023). The value of organizations

like Microsoft transcends tangible assets, resting on intangible intellectual capabilities and the ability to convert these into profitability (Jiang, Guo, He, & Chen, 2025). Knowledge organizations harness their intellectual capital, providing a competitive edge through their expertise, and can drive value-adding innovations across various sectors, from high technology to financial services (Ding et al., 2023).

H4: Ambidextrous Organization mediates the relationship between Ambidextrous Human capital and organizational performance.

H5: Ambidextrous Organization mediates the relationship between Ambidextrous Relational capital and organizational performance.

H6: Ambidextrous Organization mediates the relationship between Ambidextrous Structural capital and organizational performance.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

Expanded Conceptual Framework

Figure 3: Expanded Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopts a two-stage approach to realize its objectives. In the first stage, a comprehensive approach is applied to develop a measure for AIC. This task is accomplished by adopting a two-step approach, as illustrated in Table 1. In the second stage, data are collected from 700 SMEs in the manufacturing sector by using a close-ended questionnaire. The AIC variable comprises one part of the developed questionnaire. The remaining construct are adopted from extant studies. After data collection, partial least squares structural equation modeling is directed to examine the modeled relationships. The succeeding section explains each step-in detail Table 1.

Table 1 Scale Development Decision Tree (SDDT)

1.	Identification and Selection of Dimensions AIC
a)	Identification of dimensions and sub-dimensions
d)	Selection of dimensions and sub-dimensions
c)	Item generation based on selected dimensions and sub-dimensions
2.	Employing Exploratory Factor Analysis
a)	Determine the sampling procedure
b)	Data Collection Methods
c)	Data cleaning and factorability
d)	Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity
e)	KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin)
f)	Rotate factors

 g) Varimax rotations

Identification and Selection of Dimensions AIC

Identification

The quality of a gauge relies on the scholar's judgment, which comprises the selection of dimensions. Forza and Sandrin (2023) argued that “*The apparent simplicity and efficiency of the survey method can be illusionary, as much time and consideration is needed to develop a measure that allows us to make reliable and valid inferences about respondents*”. Meaningful measurement occurs when the questions successfully achieve the intended representation of the abstract construct of AIC. When operationalizing an abstract construct, finding the representative sample of items and dimensions to represent its abstractness is essential. Lambert and Newman (2023) referred to this process as meaning analysis, in which a theoretician adopts logical procedures to justify the conceptual and operational definitions of a construct. The current dissertation addresses the validity of the concept before methodological applications and statistical analyses by addressing the labeling of the AIC Construct and its sub-dimensions, i.e., ambidextrous HC (AHC), ambidextrous RC (ARC), and ambidextrous SC (ASC), creating conceptual definitions, understanding the breadth of the Construct, and generating and refining items for the scale. This study follows the method of (Mubarik, Chandran, & Devadason, 2018; Odhano, Mahmood, Naqvi, & Ahmed, 2025) in which an extensive sample of items is first generated and then all the domains and dimensions of the construct are configured. After configuring the items of the construct, a pretest is conducted to check the preliminary validity of the questionnaire. After the pretest, the questionnaire is sent to the respondents for data collection.

Sampling Experts

Experts are selected to solicit their opinions about selecting the appropriate dimensions and sub-dimensions of IC. We apply non-probability sampling techniques (expert sampling) to select SME experts. This technique is adopted for two reasons. First, we target SME experts and second, we require experts with experience and expertise in this research, necessitating a deliberate selection of sample units. Table 2 provides the expert selection criteria. A total of 90 experts are selected for the preliminary survey and the rating. Table 2 presents the details of the expert sampling.

Table 2 Expert Selection Category and Experts Sampled

Experts	Inclusion criterion	Detailed description	Number sampled	Total
Governments Officials	10 years of experience in top management	Government officials, who work in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning Commission of Pakistan 	1	20

	capacities dealing with SMEs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs Development Authority (SMEDA) • State Bank of Pakistan • Trade Development Authority of Pakistan (TDA) 	15	
Experts form Institutions	05 years' experience in teaching as a subject specialist and industrial expert from Non-profit organizations.	Professionals experts who work in the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia (Subject Specialist) • Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) 	8	16
Industrial Professionals	10 years of expertise in Top Management Teams dealing with SMEs especially in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan.	Professionals who work in the manufacturing sector of SMEs in Pakistan: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Textile • Leather • Food • Metal • Furniture • Sports 	17	54
			03	
			11	
			4	
			6	
			13	
Total				90

Data Collection from SMEs Experts for the Preliminary Survey

We developed a questionnaire for the original survey based on the potential dimensions from Chapter 4, consisting of 501 dimensions aimed at evaluating HC, RC, and SC, with 197, 147, and 157 items respectively. This questionnaire underwent assessment by 10 experts, leading to revisions that finalized the items for data collection.

Selection of Dimensions and Sub-Dimensions

Criteria to Select Relevant Dimensions and Sub-dimensions

The process of selecting the pertinent items was based on the weighted mean score criterion. The rating provided by the respondents were revalued based on the proportion of the respondent chose that score. For instance, if 20% of the respondents rated an item one, 50% rated it 2 and the remaining 30% rated it 30. The final mean rating was found by multiplying their rating with these percentages

and adding the resultant products. This procedure has been previously adopted by (Mandil, Salih, & Muhsen, 2024; Mubarik, Govindaraju, & Devadason, 2016). Mathematically, this expression can be written as follows:

$$MV = \%NI*1 + \%SWI*2 + \%VI*3,$$

Once the mean has been computed, it was set as a cutoff point for selecting relevant dimensions. The average of highest and lowest was considered as a cutoff point in the study at hand. *Item*

Generation Based on Selected Dimensions and Sub-Dimensions

The item selection process is iterative, as chosen items significantly influence the final scale. It begins with defining the construct and involves selecting relevant items, supported by extensive literature reviews to avoid errors in inclusion or exclusion. Items must be clear, concise, and distinct, accurately reflecting the construct's meaning. Expert feedback is essential for item generation and dimension identification (Lambert & Newman, 2023).

Application of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

After collecting data from the respondents, the dataset is inspected to remove missing numbers, outliers, and unengaged responses (Ward & Meade, 2023). After examination, data are processed for EFA. The first step of EFA is the application of the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett's test of sphericity. These tests are used to inspect sampling adequacy and examine the appropriateness of EFA. Inferring from the theoretical exposition, this research regards AIC as a second-order measurement model that encompasses three dimensions: AHC, ARC, and ASC. In multivariate statistics based on the two-dimensionality approach: The first stage is Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). This factor analysis approach has the primary objective of identifying underlying relationships among AIC. Scholars commonly use EFA when developing construct and scales (Widaman & Helm, 2023). In the second stage, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is performed to detect the dimensionality of the three scales that will be used to measure AIC (Howard & O'Sullivan, 2024). Scale reliability measures the internal consistency and stability of scales, highlighting that multi-item scales are more reliable than single-item scales. The research addresses potential biases in top management's perceptions by standardizing scale reliability using two methods: the test-retest procedure and the composite reliability (CR) coefficient. The study involved administering the same test to 90 respondents twice, 30 days apart, to assess score consistency. Of the 30 firms that participated in the retest exercise, 3 responses were excluded, resulting in an 80.2% final response rate (Goretzko, 2023). The reliability of the measurement was evaluated using the CR coefficient, with results of 0.7 or higher for each dimension, indicating acceptable reliability. Despite some items showing a reliability coefficient of 0.50, they were retained to ensure content validity. (Howard, 2023) indicated that the extraction method evaluates the covariation/correlation among all the scale items and aims to extract latent variables from manifest variables. Statistical package options include unweighted least squares, maximum likelihood, generalized least squares, alpha factoring, image factoring, and principal axis factoring. An eigenvalue greater than one signifies the total variance described by each factor. The most frequently supported approach when assessing factor numbers is

the eigenvalue-greater-than-one rule (Sellbom & Goretzko, 2023). (Govindasamy et al., 2024) believed that eigenvalues higher than one result in stable dimensions. A Scree plot is a plot of eigenvalues versus the number of factors or variables in order of extraction. For factor rotation, the varimax procedure is adopted by most researchers. In this research, Axes are maintained at the right angles. Orthogonal rotation generates uncorrelated factors (Ahmed & Maruod, 2025; Widaman & Helm, 2023). Ideally, researchers embrace approximately three times as many items in a questionnaire as those that will be included in the final scale based on minimum factor item loadings and the correlations between variables and factors. In this study, simple factor structure is frequently determined based on several pre-established general criteria: factor item loadings at or above the 0.30–0.50 levels (Serra, Alves, & Pinheiro, 2025; Turan, Özer, & Karman, 2023).

Population & Sampling

In this cross-sectional study, primary data was collected via questionnaires from top management professionals in the manufacturing sector of SMEs in Pakistan, examining three independent variables, one mediating variable, one dependent variable, and various demographic variables. According to the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA) of Pakistan (2018), SMEs represent 99% of over 3.2 million businesses and contribute 35% of the value added to the economy. SMEs are crucial for economic development, accounting for 30% of GDP, 25% of exports, and 78% of industrial employment, thereby indicating a direct relationship between SME growth and economic progression (Khan, Ming, Ali, & Zhang, 2022). Currently, 6.76 million SMEs exist in Pakistan, predominantly in Punjab (61%) and Sindh (36%), with 68% engaged in wholesale, retail, restaurants, and hotels, while 26% operate in manufacturing. The data illustrates that SMEs in Pakistan collectively represent about 40% of GDP and over 40% of exports, with most being operational for less than 20 years, underscoring their significant economic role (N. Ali, Butzbach, Katohar, & Afridi, 2024). Provincial wise distribution of SMEs in exhibited table 3.

Table 3 Provincial Distribution of SMEs (SMEDA)

Pakistan	6.76 Million (SMEs)
Punjab	61%
Sindh	36 %
KPK	14%
Baluchistan	04%

Sampling Procedure: Cluster Sampling

We focus on manufacturing sector SMEs, which are approximately 1 million. However, registered SMEs manufacturing is only 20,550. The Census of Manufacturing Industries (2005–2006) reported 72 districts in Pakistan. Among these, 10 districts, namely, Faisalabad, Gujranwala, Gujrat, Karachi, Hyderabad, Lahore, Multan, Sialkot, Sheikhupura, and Quetta, account for major clusters of SMEs (more than 50%). Furthermore, 25% of SMEs in the country are in Karachi, Lahore, and Faisalabad districts. Using the cluster sampling techniques previously adopted by (Rehman, Elrehail, Nair,

Bhatti, & Taamneh, 2023). In this regard, 624 firms from 6 major industries were selected as the sample for this study. The citywide distribution of the selected samples was obtained along with the number of SMEs registered in that city (SMEDA).

Table 4 Industry Base Sampling Distribution

S. No.	Industry	Percentage	Number of Firms
1	Textile	26	165
2	Leather	16	100
3	Sports	13	86
4	Food	24	146
5	Metal	08	48
6	Furniture	13	79
Total		100	624

Table 5 Demographic Distribution of sample City wise

Cluster	Firms Count	Share Proportion wise	Number of Companies Sampled
Karachi	4777	0.232	147
Lahore	4433	0.216	136
Gujranwala	2927	0.142	88
Faisalabad	2717	0.132	83
Sialkot	1993	0.097	59
Multan	1132	0.055	32
Gujrat	984	0.048	30
Sheikhupura	973	0.047	29
Hyderabad	553	0.027	16
Quetta	61	0.003	02
Peshawar	60	0.003	02
Total	20550	1	624 (useable)

Survey Instrument Development

A survey was designed to incorporate AIC, AO, and OP as construct of the conceptual model. The survey was developed to collect primary data from a large number of respondents. This tool is reliable, and thus, is widely used by social science researchers in data collection. Data were unavailable; hence, we developed a close-ended questionnaire for collecting data. The questionnaire includes two major parts. Part A consists of 8 questions about the firm's demographic profile, and Part B has 132 rating questions related to 93 measures of AIC, including 34 for AHC, 27 for ASC, and 32 for ARC. Similarly, 18 questions about a firm's AOs and 27 questions for measuring the five performance dimensions of a firm are included.

All the items in Part B are measured using a seven-point Likert-type scale. This part mostly includes questions with ordinal-level responses, such as “Strongly Disagree” (1), “Disagree” (2), “Somewhat Disagree” (3), “Indifferent/Neutral” (4), “Somewhat Agree” (5), “Agree” (6), and “Strongly Agree” (7).

Table 6 Operationalization of the Variables

Construct	Number of Dimensions	Number of items	Source(s)
Organizational Performance	Technological Process	3	Al-Jinini et al., (2019); Antonelli & Colombelli, (2011); Delgado-Verde et al., (2016); Zmud & Apple, (1991)
	Export Performance	5	Sousa et al., (2008); Steven White et al., 1998, 1998; Wagner, (1995)
	Productivity Improvements	6	Black & Lynch, (1996); Kengatharan, (2019); Sharabati et al., (2010)
	Innovation	7	Andriopoulos & Lewis, (2010); Delgado-Verde et al., (2016); Oke, (2007); Rosenbusch et al., (2011)
Ambidextrous Organization	Survivability	6	Gimeno et al., (1997); Hill & Birkinshaw, (2014); Taylor & Helfat, (2009)
	Exploration	9	Andriopoulos & Lewis, (2009); Gilsing & Duysters, (2008); Raisch et al., (2009); Stettner & Lavie, (2014)
	Exploitation	9	Avent-Holt, (2015); Geerts et al., (2010); Gupta et al., (2006); Rajan, (1990)

Pilot Testing of the Instrument

The study used a threefold approach to confirm the validity of the instrument. The first draft of the questionnaire was sent to consultants of Pakistan’s manufacturing sector. Their feedback considerably helped improve the fitness of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was then rotated among relevant manufacturing professionals to check for any inappropriate items. The professionals were also asked to recommend new items, which helped us in further improving the questionnaire. During the third stage, the questionnaire was sent to relevant manufacturing sectors. Finally, the PLS-SEM measurement model helped us verify the reliability and validity of the questionnaire. We

observed that the factor loadings of the indicators meet the threshold values, i.e., above 0.708, demonstrating that the instrument is fit and free from abnormality.

Partial least Square (PLS)-Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

This study adopted PLS-SEM to obtain solutions even with a small sample size when models include many construct and numerous items (Khan, Rashid, Rasheed, & Amirah, 2023). (Rashid, Rasheed, Ngah, Pradeepa Jayaratne, et al., 2024) pointed out that previous research on the requirements of sample size in PLS-SEM disregarded the fact that this technique is sound and valuable for analyzing huge quantities of data. PLS-SEM offers numerous possible ways to analyze big datasets, including secondary data. Several scholars have specified that the lack of distributional assumptions is the primary reason for selecting PLS-SEM (Guenther, Guenther, Ringle, Zaefarian, & Cartwright, 2023). This study adopted PLS-SEM to prove that it is a valuable resource for examining secondary data from the perspective of measurement theory. SEM has become popular, and it fulfills the need to assess complete theories and concepts. The SEM method can estimate the measurement of latent variables and test the connections between latent variables (S. Khan, Rashid, Rasheed, & Amirah, 2023). This work used SEM to analyze the relationship among variables. SEM makes using these statistical techniques for simultaneously analyzing the connection among numerous variables easier for scholars (Becker, Cheah, Gholamzade, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2023). Thus, this study associated AIC directly with OP and through AO.

Results and Findings

This research presents the results of the study obtained by applying the first stage of the methodology, as explained in Chapter 4. It includes the findings on the development of AIC. The analysis was conducted in two parts. The first part pertains to the proposition of the AIC construct on the literature review and the preliminary analysis results. The second part presents the results of the application of EFA to scale development. SPSS software (version 22.0) was used to conduct EFA.

Construct Development

The entire scale development process was divided into three major parts. The first part is the identification of the relevant dimensions and sub-dimensions of AIC. The second part is the selection of the relevant dimensions of AIC. The third part is the generation of items to operationalize the dimensions and sub-dimensions, and thus, EFA is conducted to determine the final Construct. Subsequently, 11 keywords were identified to search for relevant studies on IC and OA in Tables 6, 7 and 8.

Table 6 Keywords on Intellectual capital and organizational ambidexterity

S.No.	Keywords
1	Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital
2	Intellectual Capital Ambidexterity

3	Exploitation Intellectual Capital
4	Exploration Intellectual Capital
5	Exploration and Exploitation Intellectual Capital
6	Intellectual Capital Ambidextrous
7	IC and OA
8	OA and IC
9	HC Ambidexterity
10	RC Ambidexterity
11	SC Ambidexterity

Table 7 Repository wise Articles Accessed and Selected for Meta-Analysis

S.No.	Repository	Number of search results obtained	Selected for Abstract Review	Selected for Meta-Analysis
1	Emerald insight	25113	259	89
2	SAGE Journals	66801	123	36
3	Springer Link	8041	89	27
4	Taylor & Francis	146177	63	39
5	Science Direct	28032	107	25
6	IEEE	300	79	22
7	Elsevier's	558	53	23
8	Wiley	699	86	19
Total	8	275,721	859	280

Table 8 Keyword wise Articles selected from each Repository

S.No.	Keywords	Emerald insight	SAGE Journals	Springer Link	Taylor & Francis	Science Direct	IEEE	Elsevier	Wiley	Total
1	Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital	5	5	9	3	1	0	1	2	25
2	Intellectual Capital Ambidexterity	7	2	7	6	5	3	3	5	38
3	Exploitation Intellectual Capital	5	9	8	4	3	2	2	2	35

4	Exploration Intellectual Capital	9	4	4	9	4	1	3	1	35
5	Exploration and Exploitation Intellectual Capital	8	13	4	3	2	2	2	3	37
6	Intellectual Capital Ambidextrous	6	2	6	1	1	0	2	2	20
7	Intellectual Capital Exploration and Exploitative	6	9	3	1	1	2	3	2	27
8	Intellectual Capital and organizational Ambidexterity	6	12	6	1	3	3	5	5	41
9	Human Capital Ambidexterity	10	1	4	5	2	1	3	3	29
10	Relational Capital Ambidexterity	4	22	1	3	1	0	2	2	35
11	Structural capital Ambidexterity	2	18	3	2	1	1	5	3	25

Selection of the Dimensions and Sub-dimensions of AIC through a Preliminary Survey

A preliminary survey was conducted by developing a questionnaire based on the 03 scales (03 *for important to 01 for not important*). Questionnaires were sent to 90 selected experts. A detailed discussion of the preliminary survey questionnaire and experts' selection is provided in Chapter 3. All the potential dimensions of IC, i.e., HC, RC, and SC, were added to the questionnaire. Then, experts were asked to rate each dimension in accordance with its importance in its respective dimensions. The results of the first survey on respondents' opinions regarding IC are exhibited in Table 7 cutoff values, respectively the dimensions of HC, RC, and SC. The results are arranged in descending order of their mean values

Table 7.1 Summary of cutoff values on Human Capital

Human Capital	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Very Important	Mean Value
Education	0.01	0.57	2.10	2.69
Experience	0.03	0.57	2.06	2.66
Expertise	0.06	0.54	2.01	2.61
Skills	0.07	0.54	1.97	2.59
Training	0.06	0.57	1.97	2.60

Creativity	0.09	0.54	1.93	2.56
Attitudes	0.07	0.57	1.93	2.57
Abilities	0.06	0.60	1.93	2.59
Compliance	0.09	0.57	1.89	2.54
Health	0.06	0.60	1.89	2.54
Capability	0.07	0.66	1.89	2.61
Stability	0.11	0.54	1.84	2.50
Management ability to assume risk	0.43	0.46	1.03	1.91
Employee diversity	0.40	0.51	1.03	1.94
Behavioral performance	0.40	0.63	0.94	1.97
Employees' turnover rate	0.36	0.66	0.94	1.96
Occupational assessment	0.47	0.46	0.90	1.83
Information and learn	0.40	0.60	0.90	1.90
Risk taking ability	0.39	0.63	0.90	1.91
Openness to the experience	0.37	0.66	0.90	1.93
Individual's age	0.43	0.57	0.86	1.86
Team-buildings	0.43	0.57	0.86	1.86
Act as a model for others	0.40	0.63	0.86	1.89
Equipped workers	0.40	0.63	0.86	1.89
Open to experience	0.40	0.63	0.86	1.89
Teamwork training	0.40	0.63	0.86	1.89
Turnover rate	0.40	0.63	0.86	1.89
ICT skills	0.39	0.66	0.86	1.90
Small entrepreneur capability	0.39	0.66	0.86	1.90
Technical training	0.39	0.66	0.86	1.90
Group learning	0.37	0.69	0.86	1.91
Employees' original ideas	0.21	0.89	0.86	1.96
Ability to manage change	0.46	0.54	0.81	1.81

Risk-Taking and problem-solving capabilities	0.46	0.54	0.81	1.81
Implicit Knowledge	0.44	0.57	0.81	1.83
Specialist	0.44	0.57	0.81	1.83
Strategic view of the firm	0.44	0.57	0.81	1.83
Technological Readiness	0.44	0.57	0.81	1.83
Time spend on training	0.44	0.57	0.81	1.83
Work environment	0.44	0.57	0.81	1.83
Entrepreneurial experience	0.43	0.60	0.81	1.84
Ethics values and moral rules	0.43	0.60	0.81	1.84
Labor training	0.43	0.60	0.81	1.84
Planning	0.43	0.60	0.81	1.84
Proactive behavior in critical situations	0.43	0.60	0.81	1.84
Work System effectiveness	0.43	0.60	0.81	1.84
Absorptive capacity	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
Career development	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
Decision-maker	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
Off-the-job training	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
On-the-job learning	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
Reputation of employees	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
Work related skills	0.41	0.63	0.81	1.86
Cognitive ability	0.40	0.66	0.81	1.87
Labor productivity	0.40	0.66	0.81	1.87
Technical skills	0.40	0.66	0.81	1.87
Wisdom	0.40	0.66	0.81	1.87
Sharing and reporting knowledge	0.39	0.66	0.81	1.86
Ability to plan long-term	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Charges on employees	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Degree of development of new ideas and knowledge	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89

High performance worker	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Intrinsic motivation	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
On the Job Training	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Psychometric assessment	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Team dynamics	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Commitment	0.37	0.71	0.81	1.90
Employee commitment	0.37	0.71	0.81	1.90
Faithfulness	0.37	0.71	0.81	1.90
Generic Human	0.37	0.71	0.81	1.90
Knowledge management	0.33	0.80	0.81	1.94
Knowledge-based innovation	0.33	0.80	0.81	1.94
Intellectual Agility	0.31	0.83	0.81	1.96
Employee behavior	0.46	0.54	0.77	1.77
Similar industry experience	0.43	0.60	0.77	1.80
Academicians capability	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Deal with strategic problems	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Function-based development	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Initiative	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Self-confidence	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Seniority (Organizational tenure)	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Teamwork	0.43	0.63	0.77	1.83
Leadership ability	0.43	0.66	0.77	1.86
Adaptability	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Cooperative behavior	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Empowerment	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Level of Education	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Planning and controlling	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Problem solving skills	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84

Trustworthiness	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Vocational qualification (Technical education)	0.41	0.66	0.77	1.84
Personal attributes	0.43	0.69	0.77	1.89
Time on training	0.43	0.69	0.77	1.89
Benefit	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Generalist	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Interpersonal training	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Quality of alma-matter	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Satisfaction	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Transmission of knowledge	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Value for knowledge	0.40	0.69	0.77	1.86
Ambidextrous learning capability	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Collaborative discussion	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Communication skills	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Cooperation	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Knowledge: Tacit and Explicit.	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Skill-based pay	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Work related experience	0.39	0.71	0.77	1.87
Competence	0.37	0.74	0.77	1.89
Knowledge-based dynamic capability	0.37	0.74	0.77	1.89
Effect on another positively	0.36	0.77	0.77	1.90
Aptitude	0.31	0.86	0.77	1.94
Develop new ideas	0.31	0.86	0.77	1.94
Innovativeness / Rate of new product or process creativity	0.30	0.89	0.77	1.96
Desirability of converting innovations	0.29	0.91	0.77	1.97
Year of services	0.47	0.57	0.73	1.77
Spending on training	0.47	0.63	0.73	1.83

Longevity	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
Supervisor training	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
Turnover	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
Vocational training	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
On the Job Training	0.39	0.69	0.81	1.89
Aggregate household income	0.43	0.66	0.73	1.81
Loyalty	0.43	0.66	0.73	1.81
Time spend on problem solving	0.43	0.66	0.73	1.81
Learning	0.41	0.69	0.73	1.83
Organizational tenure	0.41	0.69	0.73	1.83
Pervious industry experience	0.41	0.69	0.73	1.83
Previous Training	0.41	0.69	0.73	1.83
Ability to treat conflicts	0.40	0.71	0.73	1.84
Organizational memory	0.40	0.71	0.73	1.84
Quality of education	0.40	0.71	0.73	1.84
Technical education	0.40	0.71	0.73	1.84
Vision of employees	0.40	0.71	0.73	1.84
Willingness	0.40	0.71	0.73	1.84
Ability to sustain effort to achieve aims	0.39	0.74	0.73	1.86
Genetic inheritance	0.39	0.74	0.73	1.86
Knowledge sharing	0.39	0.74	0.73	1.86
Manager international experience	0.39	0.74	0.73	1.86
Job-relevant knowledge	0.36	0.80	0.73	1.89
Skill-based development	0.20	0.83	0.73	1.76
Employee motivation	0.31	0.89	0.73	1.93
Employee skills	0.31	0.89	0.73	1.93
Physically strong	0.50	0.54	0.69	1.73
Special qualification	0.50	0.54	0.69	1.73

Safety Issues	0.36	0.54	0.69	1.59
Academic records	0.49	0.57	0.69	1.74
Flexibility and horizontal fit	0.47	0.60	0.69	1.76
Charges & Litigations	0.46	0.63	0.69	1.77
Engagement	0.46	0.63	0.69	1.77
Manager orientation toward the future	0.46	0.63	0.69	1.77
Employee retention	0.44	0.66	0.69	1.79
Intuitive cognitive skills	0.44	0.66	0.69	1.79
Multi-skilled attitudes	0.44	0.66	0.69	1.79
Knowledge capital	0.43	0.69	0.69	1.80
Own value fairly	0.43	0.69	0.69	1.80
Professional skills	0.43	0.69	0.69	1.80
Knowledge creation	0.41	0.71	0.69	1.81
Mobility	0.41	0.71	0.69	1.81
Applied experience	0.41	0.74	0.69	1.84
Employee values and beliefs	0.40	0.74	0.69	1.83
knowledge-based capability	0.39	0.77	0.69	1.84
Entrepreneurial skills	0.33	0.89	0.69	1.90
Pedagogic action	0.50	0.57	0.64	1.71
Delegate authority	0.47	0.63	0.64	1.74
Working experience (Year)	0.47	0.63	0.64	1.74
Encourage acceptance of change	0.46	0.66	0.64	1.76
Job/Function-based	0.47	0.69	0.64	1.80
Personal income	0.44	0.69	0.64	1.77
Know-how	0.40	0.69	0.64	1.73
Manager professional experience	0.40	0.77	0.64	1.81
Intelligence (Cognitive ability)	0.41	0.49	0.60	1.50
Age	0.53	0.54	0.60	1.67

Age of entrepreneur	0.51	0.57	0.60	1.69
Spirit of employees	0.51	0.57	0.60	1.69
Negotiation ability	0.49	0.63	0.60	1.71
Ownership	0.49	0.63	0.60	1.71
Ability to develop consensus	0.44	0.71	0.60	1.76
Multilevel perspective capabilities	0.44	0.71	0.60	1.76
Technical qualification	0.44	0.71	0.60	1.76
Managerial capabilities	0.41	0.77	0.60	1.79
Talent management	0.40	0.80	0.60	1.80
Complaints	0.56	0.51	0.56	1.63
Technical test for recruitment	0.53	0.57	0.56	1.66
Employee sustainability	0.50	0.63	0.56	1.69
Agreeableness	0.47	0.69	0.56	1.71
No. of full-time employees	0.56	0.54	0.51	1.61
Flexibility	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Net operating revenue/total number of employees	0.59	0.51	0.47	1.57
Potential adaptability to discover	0.50	0.69	0.47	1.66
No. of part-time employees and full-time contractors	0.57	0.57	0.43	1.57
% of time spent on routinizing operations	0.61	0.51	0.39	1.51
% of full-time permanent employees / total employment	0.70	0.37	0.34	1.41
Average age	0.69	0.43	0.30	1.41
% of employees rotating in from or out to cooperation partners	0.76	0.31	0.26	1.33
Absence rate	0.81	0.23	0.21	1.26
Service workers	0.67	0.51	0.21	1.40
Absenteeism	0.76	0.37	0.17	1.30

Table 7.2 Summary of cutoff values on Relational Capital

Relational Capital	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Very Important	Mean Value
Relationships with customers (Down Stream)	0.03	0.66	1.93	2.61
Customer service	0.06	0.63	1.89	2.57
Relationships with its suppliers (Up-Stream)	0.06	0.63	1.89	2.57
Goodwill	0.07	0.60	1.89	2.56
Distribution Channels	0.06	0.66	1.84	2.56
Cooperation with universities and research institutes	0.06	0.66	1.84	2.56
Strategic Alliance	0.03	0.74	1.80	2.57
Relationships with stake holder	0.07	0.66	1.80	2.53
Internal Relationship Management	0.09	0.63	1.80	2.51
Market intelligence	0.06	0.71	1.76	2.53
Relationship with regulatory body	0.39	0.63	0.90	1.91
Relationship trade associations	0.39	0.66	0.86	1.90
Availability of cooperation agreements with other organizations	0.46	0.60	0.73	1.79
Customer complaints	0.47	0.60	0.69	1.76
Public presence of firm employees and managers in association	0.37	0.83	0.64	1.84
Customer intelligence integration	0.43	0.71	0.64	1.79
Social satisfaction	0.44	0.69	0.64	1.77
Customer profiles	0.49	0.60	0.64	1.73
New market development and investment	0.51	0.54	0.64	1.70
Social media	0.53	0.51	0.64	1.69
Closeness	0.44	0.71	0.60	1.76
Cooperative	0.47	0.66	0.60	1.73
Accessing market information	0.43	0.77	0.56	1.76

Personal relations	0.43	0.77	0.56	1.76
Image	0.46	0.71	0.56	1.73
Public spiritedness	0.51	0.60	0.56	1.67
Social relations	0.51	0.60	0.56	1.67
Firm's ability to target goal markets	0.56	0.51	0.56	1.63
Customer creation-value	0.44	0.77	0.51	1.73
Firm's ability to stabilize long-term relations of trust with suppliers	0.46	0.74	0.51	1.71
Customer type	0.49	0.69	0.51	1.69
Client services	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Employee satisfaction	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Formal and informal network ties	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Marketing channel	0.53	0.60	0.51	1.64
Social ties	0.53	0.51	0.51	1.56
Public presence of firm employees and managers in conferences and forums	0.43	0.83	0.47	1.73
Institutional ties	0.46	0.77	0.47	1.70
Industry associations	0.47	0.74	0.47	1.69
Importance of cooperation with experts and consultancy firms as a source for the creation of innovative ideas	0.44	0.74	0.47	1.66
Build deep trust and reciprocity	0.54	0.60	0.47	1.61
Social networks	0.56	0.57	0.47	1.60
Staff strength	0.57	0.54	0.47	1.59
Firm's ability to stabilize long-term relations of trust with customers	0.47	0.77	0.43	1.67
Help maintain clients	0.47	0.77	0.43	1.67
Community	0.49	0.74	0.43	1.66
Collective action	0.50	0.71	0.43	1.64
Formal and informal systems to share resources with suppliers	0.50	0.71	0.43	1.64
Reduced delays	0.50	0.71	0.43	1.64

Public presence in events in recognition of achievements	0.53	0.66	0.43	1.61
Community relations	0.54	0.63	0.43	1.60
Socializing	0.54	0.63	0.43	1.60
Client Retentions	0.56	0.60	0.43	1.59
Ego-network	0.56	0.60	0.43	1.59
Environmental dynamism	0.56	0.60	0.43	1.59
New ventures	0.56	0.60	0.43	1.59
Social structures	0.56	0.60	0.43	1.59
Sociological institutional concept	0.56	0.60	0.43	1.59
Market share	0.59	0.54	0.43	1.56
Social atmosphere	0.59	0.54	0.43	1.56
Number of customer complaints	0.64	0.46	0.43	1.53
Corporate actions	0.44	0.86	0.39	1.69
Customer response time	0.47	0.80	0.39	1.66
Reputation	0.51	0.71	0.39	1.61
Shared representations	0.51	0.71	0.39	1.61
Firm's More communicative	0.53	0.69	0.39	1.60
Shared vision	0.53	0.69	0.39	1.60
Benevolence	0.56	0.63	0.39	1.57
Firm's ability to develop cooperation agreements	0.56	0.63	0.39	1.57
Customer outflow	0.57	0.60	0.39	1.56
Business partnership	0.60	0.54	0.39	1.53
Cognitive social capital	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Diversity of contacts	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Entrepreneurial	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Social cohesion	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Heterogeneity in partners	0.54	0.69	0.34	1.57
Values	0.54	0.69	0.34	1.57
Branding	0.56	0.66	0.34	1.56
Firm's More flexible	0.56	0.66	0.34	1.56
Welfare system	0.56	0.66	0.34	1.56
Civic institution	0.57	0.63	0.34	1.54
Social inclusion	0.59	0.60	0.34	1.53
Optimism	0.60	0.57	0.34	1.51

Internal labor market-based	0.61	0.54	0.34	1.50
Market segments	0.46	0.89	0.30	1.64
Homogenous social groups	0.51	0.77	0.30	1.59
Continual and up-to-date customer	0.60	0.66	0.30	1.56
Contractors' relationship	0.56	0.69	0.30	1.54
Firm's ability to measure its customers' attraction	0.56	0.69	0.30	1.54
Sense of alignment	0.56	0.69	0.30	1.54
Status	0.56	0.69	0.30	1.54
Strategies for competitors	0.56	0.69	0.30	1.54
Deliver consistent	0.57	0.66	0.30	1.53
Social embeddedness	0.57	0.66	0.30	1.53
Complicity	0.59	0.63	0.30	1.51
Resiliency	0.59	0.63	0.30	1.51
Structural hole	0.59	0.63	0.30	1.51
Ability to achieve effective collaboration with other organizations in R&D	0.60	0.60	0.30	1.50
Customer's loyalty	0.60	0.60	0.30	1.50
Diffusion of knowledge through publications	0.54	0.74	0.26	1.54
International alignment	0.57	0.71	0.26	1.54
Social norms	0.54	0.74	0.26	1.54
Governmental Institutions	0.57	0.69	0.26	1.51
Resolve disputes from the workplace	0.57	0.69	0.26	1.51
Firm's ability to manage strategic alliances	0.59	0.66	0.26	1.50
Flexible and versatile sharing	0.59	0.66	0.26	1.50
Interact and exchange ideas	0.59	0.66	0.26	1.50
High-level ties	0.61	0.60	0.26	1.47
Density of voluntary	0.50	0.54	0.26	1.30
Market potential	0.49	0.89	0.21	1.59
Informal and lateral networks	0.53	0.80	0.21	1.54
Ratio of net marketing expenses	0.56	0.74	0.21	1.51
Constant Updating of customer information	0.57	0.71	0.21	1.50
Social obligations	0.57	0.71	0.21	1.50

Bridging and bonding	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Client preferences	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Density of personal contacts	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Strategic alignment	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Availability of R&D cooperation agreements with other organizations	0.60	0.66	0.21	1.47
Interlinking and family support	0.61	0.63	0.21	1.46
Revenue growth rate	0.64	0.57	0.21	1.43
Average duration of Customer relationship	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Degree of development of activity for informing and training customers	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Dissemination	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Obtain information from suppliers and subcontractors	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
On-time delivery	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Ecosystem services	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Obtaining information from present customers and markets	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Psychological institutional concept	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Availability and effectiveness of communication systems with suppliers	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Micro and macro level institutional behavior	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Orientation toward contact with the firm's main supplier	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Social knowledge integration	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Supplier intelligence integration	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Market-oriented	0.57	0.77	0.13	1.47
Product acceptance rate	0.57	0.77	0.13	1.47
Customer-focused	0.59	0.74	0.13	1.46
Inducement / Stimulus	0.61	0.71	0.13	1.46
Strategically integration	0.59	0.74	0.13	1.46
Customer's needs and requirements	0.49	0.77	0.13	1.39
Product sale concentration	0.66	0.60	0.13	1.39
Political action	0.57	0.80	0.09	1.46

Weak – ties	0.63	0.71	0.04	1.39
-------------	------	------	------	------

Table 7.3 Summary of cutoff values on Structural Capital

Structural Capital	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Very Important	Mean Value
Intellectual property rights (IPR)	0.01	0.66	1.97	2.64
Research and Development (R&D)	0.01	0.69	1.93	2.63
Business process re-engineering (BPR)	0.06	0.63	1.89	2.57
Working Systems	0.06	0.66	1.84	2.56
Brand and trademark reputation	0.07	0.63	1.84	2.54
Databases	0.01	0.77	1.80	2.59
Portfolio management	0.06	0.69	1.80	2.54
Internal management Systems	0.04	0.74	1.76	2.54
Managerial philosophies	0.06	0.71	1.76	2.53
Organizational structure	0.09	0.66	1.76	2.50
Competitive intelligence	0.36	0.71	0.86	1.93
Management enhancement and support structures	0.46	0.54	0.81	1.81
Inter-departmental rotation	0.49	0.49	0.81	1.79
Job rotations	0.44	0.60	0.77	1.81
Non-human storehouses	0.44	0.60	0.77	1.81
Inducement	0.47	0.54	0.77	1.79
Authentication Process	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
Monitoring system	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
Rate of material	0.44	0.63	0.73	1.80
Deregulation	0.51	0.49	0.73	1.73
New business strategy	0.44	0.66	0.69	1.79
Serendipitous job design	0.46	0.63	0.69	1.77
Deregulating environment	0.50	0.54	0.69	1.73

Internationalization	0.49	0.60	0.64	1.73
Tracking activity	0.49	0.60	0.64	1.73
Working capital turnover	0.49	0.60	0.64	1.73
Idiosyncratic job design	0.51	0.54	0.64	1.70
New Product	0.44	0.71	0.60	1.76
Ritual activities that positively reflect the firm's values	0.46	0.69	0.60	1.74
Transparency	0.47	0.66	0.60	1.73
Firm's records	0.49	0.63	0.60	1.71
Protocols	0.49	0.63	0.60	1.71
Cultural relevance	0.49	0.66	0.56	1.70
Trademarks	0.49	0.66	0.56	1.70
Enterprise and personnel's own commitments	0.51	0.60	0.56	1.67
Product's commercial differentiation	0.44	0.77	0.51	1.73
Fixed asset Turnover	0.49	0.69	0.51	1.69
Organizational design	0.49	0.69	0.51	1.69
Rotation of tasks and jobs	0.49	0.69	0.51	1.69
Communication and transmission systems	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Culture atmosphere	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Documentation in the product creation process	0.51	0.63	0.51	1.66
Access to raw materials	0.53	0.60	0.51	1.64
Total assets turnover	0.54	0.57	0.51	1.63
Patents and copyrights	0.44	0.80	0.47	1.71
Positive symbols	0.44	0.80	0.47	1.71

Product diversification	0.49	0.71	0.47	1.67
Managerial institution	0.50	0.69	0.47	1.66
Opaque quality	0.47	0.71	0.47	1.66
Mechanisms	0.51	0.66	0.47	1.64
Egalitarian pay structures	0.56	0.57	0.47	1.60
Institutional density	0.56	0.57	0.47	1.60
Management cost	0.59	0.51	0.47	1.57
Personnel commitment to the organization strategy	0.49	0.74	0.43	1.66
Behavioral models which employees can imitate	0.51	0.69	0.43	1.63
Codifying Systems	0.51	0.69	0.43	1.63
New marketing techniques	0.51	0.69	0.43	1.63
Organizational atmosphere	0.51	0.69	0.43	1.63
Defining tasks and jobs	0.54	0.63	0.43	1.60
Familiar technologies	0.54	0.63	0.43	1.60
Firm's Life	0.54	0.63	0.43	1.60
Variety of tasks	0.59	0.54	0.43	1.56
Information system	0.50	0.74	0.39	1.63
Architecture for retaining	0.51	0.71	0.39	1.61
Management style	0.53	0.69	0.39	1.60
Materials efficiency	0.53	0.69	0.39	1.60
New production techniques	0.53	0.69	0.39	1.60
Multiple strategy of licensing	0.54	0.66	0.39	1.59
Degree of advantage taken from individual tacit knowledge	0.50	0.77	0.34	1.61

Performance-based compensation plan	0.50	0.77	0.34	1.61
Reward systems	0.50	0.77	0.34	1.61
Degree of advantage taken from environmental knowledge	0.51	0.74	0.34	1.60
Corporate strategy	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Degree of advantage taken from organizational knowledge	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Systems of socialization	0.53	0.71	0.34	1.59
Organizational ritual	0.54	0.69	0.34	1.57
Error avoiding system	0.56	0.66	0.34	1.56
Hierarchical pay structures	0.59	0.60	0.34	1.53
Licenses	0.59	0.60	0.34	1.53
Systematic approach	0.51	0.77	0.30	1.59
Organizational functions	0.54	0.71	0.30	1.56
Promotion system	0.54	0.71	0.30	1.56
General acceptance of the commitment to achieve goals	0.56	0.69	0.30	1.54
Company image	0.56	0.71	0.26	1.53
Easily accessible information system	0.56	0.71	0.26	1.53
Organizational values	0.57	0.69	0.26	1.51
Capacity to assimilate useful new technologies and innovation, which have proven potential	0.60	0.63	0.26	1.49
New managerial techniques	0.54	0.77	0.21	1.53
Occupational health and safety	0.54	0.77	0.21	1.53
Diversified product portfolio	0.56	0.74	0.21	1.51
Organizational learning	0.56	0.74	0.21	1.51
Public image of the firm	0.56	0.74	0.21	1.51

Operations	0.57	0.71	0.21	1.50
Professional development policies	0.57	0.71	0.21	1.50
Corporate operating efficiency	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Degree of implementation of long-term formal and informal systems	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Entrepreneurial culture	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Inter-organizational processes	0.59	0.69	0.21	1.49
Business process management	0.61	0.63	0.21	1.46
Create and defend product patents	0.61	0.63	0.21	1.46
Aligned and balanced	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Core value and beliefs	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Cultural intelligence	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Decentralized and informal control and coordination processes	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Feedback mechanism	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Firm's brands	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Internal business processes	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Management systems	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
New delivery process	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
New production process	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Reputation as a leading firm	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Socio-ecological system	0.56	0.77	0.17	1.50
Acceptance of evaluation, promotion and reward criteria	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Firm's market symbols	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Manufacturing lead time	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49

Mechanistic	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Reputation as a cutting-edge technology firm	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Set of guides	0.57	0.74	0.17	1.49
Employee participation in strategic decisions	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Monitors IPRs portfolio	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Performance of patents in external or internal processes	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Supportive infrastructures	0.59	0.71	0.17	1.47
Formulas	0.60	0.69	0.17	1.46
Reputation as a quality firm	0.60	0.69	0.17	1.46
Technology allocation	0.60	0.69	0.17	1.46
Concessions	0.61	0.66	0.17	1.44
Inter-disciplinary work practice	0.61	0.66	0.17	1.44
Product's technological differentiation	0.54	0.83	0.13	1.50
New products/services	0.56	0.80	0.13	1.49
Organic	0.56	0.80	0.13	1.49
Reputation as an innovative firm	0.56	0.80	0.13	1.49
Maintaining patent rights	0.57	0.77	0.13	1.47
Structural-organizational intelligence	0.57	0.77	0.13	1.47
Manuals	0.59	0.74	0.13	1.46
Operational norms	0.59	0.74	0.13	1.46
Processes	0.59	0.74	0.13	1.46
Firm Size	0.60	0.71	0.13	1.44
High-trust environment	0.60	0.71	0.13	1.44

Just-in-time	0.60	0.71	0.13	1.44
Creation of ideas to innovate based on non-built-in technology	0.61	0.69	0.13	1.43
Innovative solutions	0.61	0.69	0.13	1.43
Internal benchmarking procedures	0.61	0.69	0.13	1.43
Procedure's support	0.61	0.69	0.13	1.43
Organizational systems	0.54	0.86	0.09	1.49
New service idea	0.56	0.83	0.09	1.47
Digitalize	0.59	0.77	0.09	1.44
Renewal and Development	0.59	0.77	0.09	1.44
Routines	0.59	0.77	0.09	1.44
Exploitative processes	0.60	0.74	0.09	1.43
System/subsystem model or prototype	0.60	0.74	0.09	1.43
Acquiring patent rights	0.61	0.71	0.09	1.41
Creation of innovative ideas expressed in patents	0.63	0.69	0.09	1.40
Products innovation	0.59	0.80	0.04	1.43
Explorative processes	0.61	0.74	0.04	1.40
Inventions	0.66	0.66	0.04	1.36

Exploratory Factor Analysis for Ambidextrous Human Capital (AHC)

Step 1 Data Collection

The literature review generated items were incorporated into the questionnaire to collect data for AHC. Initially, there were 72 items used to measure Ambidextrous Human Capital (AHC) on seven points Likert scale (7-strongly agree to 1-strongly disagree). The use of the interval scale, as being used in the current study, is appropriate for EFA.

Step 2: Defining Sampling Procedure

The data required for the study could only be collected from people with an appropriate level of knowledge, so expert sampling is the logical choice. The close-ended questionnaire was sent to 620 experts, and finally, 549 useful questionnaires were obtained.

Step 3: Examine Data Quality

Finally, the last issue related to data is the appropriateness of the collected data. Finally, the value of KMO is 0.889 more than 0.5, hence empirically confirming that the items can be reduced to fewer construct.

Step 4: Verify the factorability of the data

Once the data was cleaned, the next step was to check the factorability of the data. Doing so ascertains the suitability of the data for the exploratory factor analysis.

Table 8.1 Factorability of the AHC Data

Criteria	Measure	Value
KMO	KMO Value	0.889
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	26257.587
	Df	2556
	Sig.	0.000

The minimum KMO required is 0.6 (Kaiser & Rice, 1974). The value of 0.889 is in excess of 0.6, thus providing empirical proof of suitability of the data for EFA.

Step 5: Factor extraction

The study employed the Eigenvalue criterion for extracting the factors. All the factors that have the Eigenvalue of more than 1, were included in the measure. Table 8.2 shows the Eigenvalues of the construct and their relative ability to explain variance in terms of percentage. The total number of factors obtained was 10. The loadings of the items on the construct are given in table 8.2.

Table 8.2 Rotation Matrix and Eigen Values

Items	Factors									
	Construct 1	Construct 2	Construct 3	Construct 4	Construct 5	Construct 6	Construct 7	Construct 8	Construct 9	Construct 10
EDU 5	.597									
EDU 6						.566				
EXT4						.598				

EXT2		.749
EXT3		.688
SKL5	.584	
SKL6	.571	
EXT1		.627
TRA	.575	
5		
EDU	.773	
1		
TRA	.617	
6		
CAP5	.613	
CAP6	.634	
EDU	.721	
2		
EDU	.702	
3		
EDU	.751	
4		
EXT5	.642	
EXT6		
ABL5	.575	
ABL6		
ATD	.606	
3		
ATD	.516	
4		
ATD	.539	
5		
ATD	.611	
6		
EXP6	.545	.599
EXP1	.675	
EXP2	.654	
EXP5	.613	
EXP3	.729	
EXP4	.630	

CRT 3	.542		
CRT 4	.542		.543
ATD 1	.527		.645
ATD 2			.739
CRT 5		.691	
CAP2		.735	
CAP3		.697	
CRT 6		.631	
CAP4		.728	
CAP1		.718	
COM 1	.540		
CRT 1			.578
COM 2			
CRT 2	.608		
COM 4			
COM 5	.555		
COM 6			
STA1	.594		
STA2			
SKL1	.671		
COM 5	.523		.536
ABL1			.714
ABL4			.588
ABL2			.751

ABL3											.593
HET 3											.534
HET 4											
HET 5											.528
SKL2											.637
HET 6											.571
TRA 1											.670
TRA 2											.697
COM 6											.563
SKL3											.643
SKL4											.625
TRA 3											.674
TRA 4											.726
STA5											.594
STA4											
STA3											
HET 2											.610
HET 1											.693
Eigen Value	14.813	11.491	4.192	2.327	2.210	1.708	1.622	1.524	1.325	1.291	
VE	20.574	15.960	5.822	3.232	3.070	2.373	2.253	2.117	1.840	1.794	
CVE	20.574	36.534	42.356	45.587	48.657	51.030	53.283	55.400	57.239	59.033	

Step 6: Rotation of Factors

Table 8.3 shows the extracted construct along with their loadings, eigenvalues, and the variance extracted. The original matrix exhibits the issue of cross-loadings. Rotation is required to resolve this issue. Varimax rotation was applied in the current study.

Table 8.3 Varimax Rotation

Factor	Name of the Factor	Items Loaded	Eigen Value	% Variance Extracted
Construct 1	Education	EDU1, EDU2, EDU3 & EDU4	14.81	20.57
Construct 2	Experience	EXP1, EXP2, EXP3 & EXP4	11.49	15.96
Construct 3	Skills	SKL1, SKL2, SKL3 & SKL4	4.19	5.82
Construct 4	Training	TRA1, TRA2, TRA3 & TRA4	2.32	3.23
Construct 5	Capabilities	CAP1, CAP2, CAP3 & CAP4	2.21	3.07
Construct 6	Expertise	EXT1, EXT2, EXT3 & EXT4	1.70	2.37
Construct 7	Abilities	ABL1, ABL2, ABL3 & ABL4	1.62	2.25
Construct 8	Attitudes	ATD1 & ATD2	1.52	2.11
Construct 9	Creativity	CRT1	1.32	1.84

Construct 10	Health	HET1 & HET2	1.29	1.79
--------------	--------	----------------	------	------

Step 7: Results of the Present Study

EFA analysis of AHC used 72 items, and principal component analysis (PCA) with the use of SPSS (version 22). An initial test of data appropriateness showed that EFA had sufficient data and the inter-item correlation level was greater than 0.3, as well as the KMO got 0.889, much higher than the 0.6 mark. The test by Bartlett ensured that the correlation matrix was factorable. PCA has determined nine factors that explain 59.03% of total variance, then Varimax rotation explaining the values. These were enabled by different scholars as follows: 1) Education; 2) Experience; 3) Skills; 4) Training; 5) Capability; 6) Expertise; 7) Abilities; 8) Creativity; and 9) Attitude. Another factor, Health, was identified as well, as a tenth factor.

Exploratory Factor Analysis for Ambidextrous Relational Capital (ARC):

Step 1: Collection of Data

The items generated from the literature review were incorporated into the questionnaire to collect data for ARC. A total of 60 items were initially used to measure ASC on a seven-point Likert scale (7-strongly agree to 1-strongly disagree). The use of an interval scale in the current study is appropriate for EFA.

Step 2: Definition of Sampling Procedure

The data required for this study can only be collected from respondents with an appropriate level of knowledge, and thus, expert sampling is the logical choice. A close-ended questionnaire was sent to 620 experts, and 549 useful questionnaires were finally obtained.

Step 3: Examination of Data Quality

The last issue related to data is the appropriateness of the collected data. The same conclusion can be drawn from a significant Bartlett's sphericity test result that showed that the items are related. The KMO value was 0.918 higher than 0.5, empirically confirming that the number of items can be reduced to fewer constructs.

Step 4: Verification of Data Factorability

Once the data are cleaned, the next step is to check their factorability. This step ascertains the suitability of the data for EFA.

Table 8.3 Factorability of the Data ARC

Criteria	Measure	Value
KMO	KMO Value	0.918

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	19468.522
	Df	1770
	Sig.	0.000

The minimum KMO required is 0.6 (Kaiser & Rice, 1974). The value of 0.918 exceeds 0.6, providing empirical proof for the suitability of the data for EFA. In addition, the significant result of Bartlett's test of sphericity indicates that the items are related to one another. The correlations of the items are mostly higher than 0.3, as presented in Table 8.3.

Step 5: Extraction of Factors

This study adopted the eigenvalue criterion for extracting factors. All the factors with an eigenvalue of more than 1 were included in the measure. Table 8.4 provides the eigenvalues of the constructs and their relative capability to explain variance in terms of percentage.

Table 8.4 Rotation Matrix and Eigen Values

items	Construct 1	Construct 2	Construct 3	Construct 4	Construct 5	Construct 6	Construct 7	Construct 8	Construct 9
DC3						.644			
DC1						.783			
DC4						.655			
DC2						.736			
IRM3					.513	.535			
IRM4					.500	.502			
SA2					.705				
SA1					.726				
SA3					.658				
SA4		.543			.564				
RSH3		.553			.486				
SA5		.629							
SA6		.683							
RC4		.700							
MI6		.654							

RC1		.711		
DC5		.678		
RC2		.716		
RC3		.713		
DC6		.690		
IRM5		.679		
IRM6		.666		
CUR5			.530	
CUR6	.413	.478	.402	
RSH4			.547	
RSH5			.549	
GW3			.613	
RSH6			.573	
GW1			.695	
GW2			.698	
MI5			.577	
GW4			.609	
RC6			.488	.400
RSH2				.438
IRM1				.680
IRM2			.689	.419
CS1			.655	
CS3			.726	
RC5	.452		.604	
MI2	.473		.505	
MI3			.493	.421
CS4			.642	
CS2	.473		.467	
CS5	.643			

CS6	.645								
RS1	.738								
RS2	.786								
RS4	.813								
RS3	.826								
RSH1	.590							.457	
GW6	.687								
GW5	.538								
CS5	.694								
MI1	.605								
RS6	.712								
RS5							.569		
CUR4							.656		
CUR3							.717		
CUR2							.718		
CUR1							.773		
Eigen Value	15.806	5.488	3.601	3.200	2.605	2.001	1.538	1.322	1.285
Variance Extracted	26.343	9.147	6.001	5.333	4.342	3.335	2.563	2.203	2.141
Cumulative Variance Extracted	26.343	35.490	41.491	46.824	51.166	54.501	57.064	59.267	61.408

Step 6: Rotation of Factors

This table shows the extracted constructs with their loadings, eigenvalues, and extracted variance. The original matrix exhibits the issue of cross-loadings. Table 8.5 provides the item loadings on the construct. The following names are given to the construct.

Table 8.5 Varimax Rotation

Factor	Name of the Factor	Items Loaded	Eigen Value	% Variance Extracted
Construct 1	Relationship with Suppliers	RS1, RS2, RS3 & RS4	15.806	26.34
Construct 2	Relationship with Customer	RC1, RC2, RC3 & RC4	5.48	9.14
Construct 3	Goodwill	GW1, GW2, GW3 & GW4	3.60	6.00
Construct 4	Customer Service	CS1, CS2, CS3 & CS4	3.20	5.33
Construct 5	Strategic Alliance	SA1, SA2, SA3 & SA4	2.60	4.34
Construct 6	Distribution Channels	DC1, DC2, DC3 & DC4	2.00	3.33
Construct 7	Cooperation with universities and research institutes	CUR1, CUR2, CUR3 & CUR4	1.53	2.56
Construct 8	Relationship with Stakeholders	RSH1 & RSH2	1.32	2.20
Construct 9	Internal Relationship Management	IRM1 & IRM2	1.28	2.14

Step 7: Presentation of Results

EFA is intended to simplify data by minimizing factors, beginning with 60 items in RC constructs. The suitability of data was checked using a KMO value of 0.918 alongside significant results of the Barlett test, which states that it was factorable. The PCA indicated that there were four components whose eigenvalues were greater than 1, and they explained a maximum variance of 61.4%. According to the scree plot, nine components were used in further analysis. These aspects are consistent with the past research and they are: Relationship with Suppliers, Relationship with Customers, Goodwill, Customer Service, Strategic Alliance, Distribution Channels, Cooperation with universities and research institutes, Relationship with Stakeholders and Relationship Management internally.

Exploratory Factor Analysis for Ambidextrous Structural Capital:**Step 1: Collection of Data**

The items generated from the literature review were incorporated into the questionnaire to collect data for ASC. A total of 60 items were initially used to measure ASC on a seven-point Likert scale (7-strongly agree to 1-strongly disagree). The use of an interval scale in the current study was appropriate for EFA.

Step 2: Definition of the Sampling Procedure

The data required for the study can only be collected from respondents with an appropriate knowledge level, and thus, expert sampling is a logical choice. A close-ended questionnaire was sent to 620 experts, and 549 useful questionnaires were finally obtained.

Step 3: Examination of Data Quality

The last issue related to data is the appropriateness of the collected data. The KMO value is 0.934 higher than 0.5, empirically confirming that the number of items can be reduced to fewer constructs.

Step 4: Verification of Data Factorability

Once the data are cleaned, the next step is to check their factorability to ascertain their suitability for EFA.

Table 8.6 Factorability of the Data ASC

Criteria	Measure	Value
KMO	KMO Value	0.934
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	22271.047
	Df	1770
	Sig.	0.000

The minimum required KMO is 0.6 (Kaiser & Rice, 1974). The value of 0.934 is higher than 0.6, providing empirical proof for the suitability of the data for EFA.

Step 5: Extraction of Factors

This study adopted the eigenvalue criterion for extracting factors. All the factors with an eigenvalue of more than 1 were included in the measure. Table 8.7 provides the eigenvalues of the construct and their relative capability to explain variance in terms of percentage.

Table 8.7 Rotation Matrix and Eigen Values

Items	Construct 1	Construct 2	Construct 3	Construct 4	Construct 5	Construct 6	Construct 7	Construct 8	Construct 9
WS4				0.697					
WS1				0.742					
WS3				0.692					

WS2		0.724	
IPR5			
IPR6			
DB5			
OS1			0.515
DB6			
BPR5			
BPR6			
IPR1	0.853		
IPR3	0.680		
IPR2	0.730		
WS5			
WS6	0.670		
BTR5			
BTR6			
RD5			
RD6			
IMS3			
IMS4			
BPR1		0.736	
IMS5			
IMS6			
IMS1			0.797
MP1			
BPR4			
BPR2		0.797	
BPR3		0.662	
MP2			0.521
IMS2			0.551
MP3			
MP4			
PM1			0.516
RD1		0.764	
RD3			
RD2		0.717	
MP5			

MP6									
IPR4	0.793								
RD4									
OS2									
OS3									
OS4									
OS5									
DB2		0.776							
DB1		0.770							
DB3		0.820							
OS6									
PM2									
PM3									
PM4									
PM5									
DB4		0.727							
PM6									
BTR4					0.675				
BTR1					0.760				
BTR3					0.699				
BTR2					0.773				
Eigen value	19.09	5.11	3.67	3.31	2.02	1.80	1.40	1.24	1.13
VE	31.82	8.52		5.52	3.36	3.00	2.33	2.06	1.88
CVE	31.82	40.35	6.12 46.47	51.99	55.35	58.36	60.69	62.75	64.63

Step 6: Rotation of Factors

The original matrix suffers from the problem of cross-loadings. Rotation is required to resolve this issue. Varimax rotation was adopted in the current study. Table 8.8 provides the item loadings on the constructs. The following names are given to the constructs.

Table 8.8 Varimax Rotation

Factor	Name of the Factor	Items Loaded	Eigen Value	% Variance Extracted
Construct 1	Intellectual Property Rights	IPR1, IPR2, IPR3 & IPR4	19.09	31.82

Construct 2	Database	DB1, DB2, DB3 & DB4	5.11	8.52
Construct 3	Business Process Reengineering	BPR1, BPR2, BPR3 & BPR4	3.67	6.12
Construct 4	Working Systems	WS1, WS2, WS3 & WS4	3.31	5.52
Construct 5	Brand and trademark reputation	BTR1, BTR2, BTR3 & BTR4	2.02	3.36
Construct 6	Research and Development	RD1 & RD2	1.8	3
Construct 7	Internal Management Systems	IMS1 & IMS2	1.4	2.33
Construct 8	Organizational Structure	OS1	1.24	2.06
Construct 9	Portfolio management	PM1	1.13	1.88

Step 7: Presentation of Results

EFA on ASC was initiated with 60 items with most of them correlating above 0.3. The KMO value was 0.934, which is bigger than the value of 0.6 and the test of Bartlett proved that the correlation matrix is factorable. PCA showed 9 factors, which have an eigenvalue greater than 1 that accounted 64.63% of the variance. The interpretability of constructs was made easy by varimax rotation. The factors are associated with the prior research, such as IPR, Database, BPR, Working Systems, Brand Reputation, R&D, Internal Management Systems, Organizational Structure, and Portfolio Management with references to the relevant literature proving their importance.

Results and Outcomes

In this analysis, the Joreskog CR procedure (1971) has been used to assess internal consistency reliability with the notion that CR values in the range of 0.60 to 0.70 are good to employment in exploratory research, whereas values of 0.70 to 0.90 are satisfactory to good reliability (Hair et al., 2019a). Comparatively, Cronbach alpha is the other measure that will give lower scores and will be

less accurate because it is not weighted. Averages variance extracted (AVE) was also used in the study to measure convergent validity with an AVE of 0.50 or above showing that 50 per cent or more of the variance is explained by the construct items (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988).

Table 9 Discriminant and Convergent, and Reliability of Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital

Construct	Indicators	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Ambidextrous Human Capital			0.924	0.936	0.595
Abilities	ABL1	0.783	0.791	0.865	0.615
	ABL2	0.797			
	ABL3	0.764			
	ABL4	0.792			
Attitudes	ATT1	0.900	0.753	0.890	0.802
	ATT2	0.891			
Capabilities	CAP1	0.739	0.795	0.867	0.620
	CAP2	0.837			
	CAP3	0.800			
	CAP4	0.700			
Creativity Education	CRE1	1	1	1	1
	EDU1	0.800	0.770	0.854	0.594
	EDU2	0.824			
	EDU3	0.710			
	EDU4	0.744			
Experience	EXP1	0.734	0.784	0.860	0.607
	EXP2	0.781			
	EXP3	0.828			
	EXP4	0.769			
Expertise	EXT1	0.877	0.746	0.855	0.666
	EXT2	0.879			
	EXT3	0.676			
Health	HEA1	0.891	0.721	0.878	0.782
	HEA2	0.877			
Skills	SKL1	0.683	0.711	0.822	0.536
	SKL2	0.750			
	SKL3	0.773			
	SKL4	0.721			

Training	TRA1	0.799	0.848	0.898	0.687
	TRA2	0.839			
	TRA3	0.852			
	TRA4	0.824			
Ambidextrous Structural Capital			0.927	0.939	0.634
Business Process Reengineering	BPR1	0.849	0.913	0.939	0.793
	BPR2	0.918			
	BPR3	0.884			
	BPR4	0.910			
Brand Trademark and Reputation	BTR1	0.873	0.852	0.899	0.690
	BTR2	0.835			
	BTR3	0.768			
	BTR4	0.844			
Databases	DB1	0.870	0.883	0.920	0.741
	DB2	0.903			
	DB3	0.857			
	DB4	0.811			
Internal Management Systems	IMS1	0.901	0.814	0.890	0.729
	IMS2	0.827			
	IMS3	0.832			
Intellectual Property Rights	IPR1	0.869	0.883	0.920	0.742
	IPR2	0.881			
	IPR3	0.895			
	IPR4	0.796			
Organizational Structure	OS1	0.764	0.821	0.895	0.741
Portfolio Management	PM1	1	1	1	1
Research and Development	R&D1	0.948	0.891	0.948	0.902
	R&D2	0.951			
Working System	WS1	0.725	0.824	0.884	0.656
	WS2	0.837			
	WS3	0.852			
	WS4	0.820			

Ambidextrous Relational Capital			0.887	0.914	0.570
Customer Services	CS1	0.860	0.875	0.915	0.728
	CS2	0.895			
	CS3	0.861			
	CS4	0.795			
Cooperation with universities and research institutes	CUR1	0.904	0.791	0.905	0.827
	CUR2	0.915			
Distribution Channels	DC1	0.880	0.884	0.920	0.743
	DC2	0.837			
	DC3	0.881			
	DC4	0.848			
Good Will	GW1	0.810	0.852	0.900	0.692
	GW2	0.853			
	GW3	0.820			
	GW4	0.844			
Internal Relationship Management	IRM1	0.932	0.846	0.929	0.867
	IRM2	0.930			
Relationship with Customers	RC1	0.764	0.854	0.890	0.669
	RC2	0.818			
	RC3	0.833			
	RC4	0.855			
Relationship with Suppliers	RS1	0.820	0.850	0.899	0.689
	RS2	0.837			
	RS3	0.844			
	RS4	0.820			
Relationship with Stakeholders	RWS1	0.898	0.772	0.898	0.814
	RWS2	0.907			
Strategic Alliance	SA1	0.875	0.872	0.913	0.723
	SA2	0.832			
	SA3	0.889			
	SA4	0.803			
Ambidextrous Organization			0.852	0.931	0.870

Exploitation	EXPLOIT1	0.802	0.796	0.860	0.551
	EXPLOIT2	0.731			
	EXPLOIT3	0.713			
	EXPLOIT4	0.728			
	EXPLOIT5	0.735			
Exploration	EXPLOR1	0.718	0.864	0.898	0.597
	EXPLOR2	0.768			
	EXPLOR3	0.871			
	EXPLOR4	0.823			
	EXPLOR5	0.736			
	EXPLOR6	0.709			
Organizational Performance			0.809	0.868	0.571
Export Performance	EP1	0.847	0.922	0.941	0.762
	EP2	0.859			
	EP3	0.868			
	EP4	0.894			
	EP5	0.896			
Innovation	INNO1	0.748	0.887	0.914	0.641
	INNO2	0.829			
	INNO3	0.836			
	INNO4	0.808			
	INNO5	0.823			
	INNO6	0.754			
Productivity Improvement	PI1	0.897	0.816	0.891	0.732
	PI2	0.884			
	PI3	0.781			
Survivability	SUR1	0.865	0.843	0.905	0.761
	SUR2	0.875			
	SUR3	0.877			
Technological Process	TP1	0.783	0.796	0.881	0.712
	TP2	0.846			
	TP3	0.898			

According to the results of hypothesis testing reported in Table 10, all the six formulated hypotheses (H1 through H6) are statistically significant. The outcome of the analysis indicates that AHC, ARC, and ASC have great direct influences on OP with the path coefficients (Beta) of 0.180, 0.285, and 0.217 respectively. All direct relationships have great significance, as the p-values equal to or less than 0.001 suggest. Moreover, the findings verify strong indirect effects through AO. The two indirect paths between AHC, ARC and ASC to OP via AO have Beta values 0.069, 0.051 and 0.055, respectively, all of which are lower than 0.005. This in-depth examination proves the relationships

between the aspects mentioned in the theoretical model to be solid and statistically significant, both when it comes to the direct effects and the mediated ones.

Table 10 Hypothesis Testing

Hypotheses	Path-Coefficients and Specific Indirect Effects					
	Path	Beta	Standard Deviation	t-value	p-value	Results
H1	AHC → OP	0.180	0.052	3.427	0.001	Supported
H2	ARC → OP	0.285	0.058	4.055	0.000	Supported
H3	ASC → OP	0.217	0.061	3.554	0.000	Supported
H4	AHC → AO → OP	0.069	0.019	3.698	0.000	Supported
H5	ARC → AO → OP	0.051	0.018	2.885	0.004	Supported
H6	ASC → AO → OP	0.055	0.017	3.187	0.001	Supported

This study found no collinearity; therefore, we examined the R^2 value of the endogenous construct. The R^2 the value measures the variance of endogenous construct. R^2 ranges from 0 to 1.

Table 11 R-Square Values

Construct	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Ambidextrous Human Capital	1	1
Ambidextrous Organization	0.897	0.897
Ambidextrous relational capital	1	1
Ambidextrous Structural Capital	1	1
Organizational Performance	1	1

Conclusion

This paper discusses the relationship between Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital (AIC) and performance of manufacturing SMEs in Pakistan. It constructs the overall AIC measure and empirically examines its influence on the Organizational Performance (OP), taking into account all its elements: human, relational, and structural capital. The study supports the fact that AIC and its components are also major promoters of OP. More so, it establishes that Ambidextrous Orientation (AO) is also a mediator in this relationship. It is proposed that, with the help of their intellectual capital that leads to the development of ambidextrous skills, SMEs may get a competitive advantage, which makes it necessary to re-consider the current organizational strategies.

Practical Implications

The study provides a configurationally view for organizations to design policies and practices that each IC dimension can cater to adequately, e.g., practices to attract ambidextrous employees and incorporate them into the recruitment process. At the group level, ASC should be created in such a manner that ARC strengthens relations and fosters collaboration among diverse employees and organizational departments through proactive actions. Moreover, interactions should be promoted to generate sound knowledge networks and modes of receiving responses should be implemented to expand knowledge exchange among employees. Lastly, AO may be established through a proficient documentation process. To do so, organization management should implement operation-specific practices to enroll employees and provide up-to-date knowledge using relevant reports, adequate databases, archives, and approved manuals.

Managerial Implications

Ambidexterity can be driven by consumers rather than by distinct resources or technologies, and AIC can play a key role in developing ambidexterity. The consensus is that building AIC to develop AO is not simple due to different OP and organizational learning models, leading to pressures and trade-offs in organizations. Hence, top-level management is required to create equilibrium when allocating resources for exploitation and exploration. Accordingly, a systematic relation should be developed with suppliers, customers, and employees. Companies invest in building stronger relations with customers and employees, but they disregard their relationship with suppliers. To have an effective RC, SMEs in Pakistan must work on their supplier relationship and plan a suitable relational strategy. Organizations must also maintain an inclusive long-term strategy for customer relation development.

Limitations and future research directions

This research paper has recognized three main weaknesses, namely, it is a single country study, the data being used is cross-sectional, bringing in only a particular time frame, and it only deals with the effects of AIC and not any other possible influences, such as financial power or market reputation. It therefore suggests that future studies should be done to increase the generalizability by repeating the research to other countries and industries. It also indicates that longitudinal panel data can be used to examine relations across time. Moreover, researchers ought to use more variables, including financial potency and asset quality, to determine whether the impact of AIC on the performance is present, and to test the model on more knowledge-intensive industries.

References

- Abbas, A., Ekowati, D., Suhariadi, F., & Anwar, A. (2024). Human capital creation: a collective psychological, social, organizational and religious perspective. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 63(3), 2168-2200.
- Abdallah, A. S., Amin, H. M., Abdelghany, M., & Elamer, A. A. (2025). Assessing competitiveness through intellectual capital research: a systematic literature review and agenda for future research. *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*, 35(1), 190-220.
- Abid, N., Dowling, M., Ceci, F., & Aftab, J. (2023). Does resource bricolage foster SMEs' competitive advantage and financial performance? A resource-based perspective. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(8), 5833-5853.
- Ahmad, R., Nawaz, M. R., Ishaq, M. I., Khan, M. M., & Ashraf, H. A. (2023). Social exchange theory: Systematic review and future directions. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 1015921.
- Ahmed, A., & Maruod, W. (2025). Comparative analysis of varimax and Promax rotation methods in exploratory factor analysis. *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*, 9(5), 501-513.
- Alfalih, A. A. (2023). The ecological impact assessment of globalization dimensions and human capital: a dynamic approach in the case of selected fossil fuel-rich countries. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(16), 47712-47726.
- Ali, N., Butzbach, O. K., Katohar, H. A., & Afridi, H. I. (2024). Structural and External Barriers to Pakistan's Economic Growth: Pathways to Sustainable Development. *World*, 5(4), 1120-1129.
- Ali, Q. B., Zin, M. L. M., & bin Ismail, S. A. (2024). The role of human capital, structural capital, and relational capital in higher education institutions performance. *Journal of Management Info*, 11(2), 185-196.
- Asiaei, K., Bontis, N., Askari, M. R., Yaghoubi, M., & Barani, O. (2023). Knowledge assets, innovation ambidexterity and firm performance in knowledge-intensive companies. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 27(8), 2136-2161.
- Asiaei, K., O'Connor, N. G., Barani, O., & Joshi, M. (2023). Green intellectual capital and ambidextrous green innovation: The impact on environmental performance. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(1), 369-386.
- Aslam, A., Mudassir, M., Ghouse, G., & Farooq, A. (2024). Introducing modern human capital model. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(2), 6099-6110.
- Auerbach, P., & Green, F. (2024). Reformulating the critique of human capital theory. *Journal of Economic Surveys*.
- Bale, P. (1981). Behaviour problems and their relationship to reading difficulty. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 4(2), 123-135.
- Bananuka, J., Tauringana, V., & Tumwebaze, Z. (2023). Intellectual capital and sustainability reporting practices in Uganda. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 24(2), 487-508.
- Becker, G. S. (1962). Investment in human capital: A theoretical analysis. *Journal of political economy*, 70(5, Part 2), 9-49.
- Beh, T. S. (2023). The Impact of Ambidextrous Leadership on Organizational Performance: A Meta-Analysis.
- Campanella, F., Serino, L., Battisti, E., Giakoumelou, A., & Karasamani, I. (2023). FinTech in the financial system: towards a capital-intensive and high competence human capital reality? *Journal of Business Research*, 155, 113376.

- Caputo, F. (2024). Human–artificial intellectual capital... beyond a fragmented perspective. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(5/6), 1026-1041.
- Chatterji, N., & Kiran, R. (2023). The influence of human, organizational and relational capital of universities on their performance: a developing economy perspective. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 24(3), 799-829.
- Chen, Y.-A., Guo, S.-L., & Huang, K.-F. (2024). Antecedents of internationalization of Taiwanese SMEs: a resource-based view. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 19(11), 3581-3600.
- Civelek, M., Krajčák, V., & Ključnikov, A. (2023). The impacts of dynamic capabilities on SMEs' digital transformation process: The resource-based view perspective. *Oeconomia Copernicana*, 14(4), 1367-1392.
- Cosa, M., Pedro, E., & Urban, B. (2024). How to assess the intellectual capital of firms in uncertain times: a systematic literature review and a proposed model for practical adoption. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(7), 1-22.
- Costa, J., Pádua, M., & Moreira, A. C. (2023). Leadership styles and innovation management: What is the role of human capital? *Administrative Sciences*, 13(2), 47.
- Dimand, A.-M., Abutabenjeh, S., Rodriguez-Plesa, E., Alkadry, M. G., & Bruns Ali, S. (2023). Human capital drivers of employee intent to innovate: The case of public procurement professionals. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 43(4), 727-753.
- Ding, Z., Li, M., Yang, X., & Xiao, W. (2023). Ambidextrous organizational learning and performance: absorptive capacity in small and medium-sized enterprises. *Management Decision*, 61(11), 3610-3634.
- Dinu, E., Vătămănescu, E.-M., Stăneiu, R.-M., & Rusu, M. (2023). An exploratory study linking intellectual capital and technology management towards innovative performance in kibs. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1356.
- Edeji, O. C. (2024). Neo-liberalism, human capital theory and the right to education: Economic interpretation of the purpose of education. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 9, 100734.
- Effendi, S., So, I. G., Setiadi, N. J., & Soepriyanto, G. (2024). How can microfinance institutions successfully navigate a competitive advantage and financial performance? Exploring the role of ambidextrous leadership and intellectual capital. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 9, 1482796.
- El Nemar, S., El-Chaarani, H., Dandachi, I., & Castellano, S. (2025). Resource-based view and sustainable advantage: a framework for SMEs. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 33(6), 798-821.
- Elmakkawy, M. H., Hassan, H., & Magdy, A. (2025). Does green intellectual capital matter for green ambidexterity? Insights from the hotel industry. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 14673584251361233.
- England, P., & Folbre, N. (2023). Reconceptualizing human capital. In *A research agenda for skills and inequality* (pp. 177-195): Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Enke, S. (1962). Economic development with unlimited and limited supplies of labour. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 14(2), 158-172.
- Forza, C., & Sandrin, E. (2023). Surveys. In *Research methods for operations and supply chain management* (pp. 76-158): Routledge.
- Friedrich, B. (2023). Leveraging Organizational Structure to Achieve Ambidexterity as a Dynamic Capability.

- Gibson, C. B., & Birkinshaw, J. (2004). The antecedents, consequences, and mediating role of organizational ambidexterity. *Academy of management Journal*, 47(2), 209-226.
- Goretzko, D. (2023). Regularized exploratory factor analysis as an alternative to factor rotation. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*.
- Govindasamy, P., Isa, N. J. M., Mohamed, N. F., Noor, A. M., Ma, L., Olmos, A., & Green, K. (2024). A systematic review of exploratory factor analysis packages in R software. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics*, 16(1), e1630.
- Grugulis, I. (2024). Human capital theory. In *A guide to key theories for human resource management research* (pp. 93-99): Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Hassan, S., Raza, S., Malik, M. F., Ishaque, A., & Fiza, M. (2023). Connecting the dots: a serial mediation of intellectual capital and organizational ambidexterity between high-performance work system and innovation performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 24(6), 1578-1603.
- Hayaeian, S., & Hesarzadeh, R. (2024). Knowledge management strategies, intellectual capital, and ambidextrous innovation capability in SMEs: Are they relevant? *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(2), 6832-6859.
- Hina, K., Khalique, M., Shaari, J. A. N., Mansor, S. A., Kashmeeri, S., & Yaacob, M. R. b. (2024). Nexus between green intellectual capital and the sustainability business performance of manufacturing SMEs in Malaysia. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(2-3), 233-252.
- Howard, M. C. (2023). A systematic literature review of exploratory factor analyses in management. *Journal of Business Research*, 164, 113969.
- Howard, M. C., & O'Sullivan, R. (2024). A systematic review of exploratory factor analysis in marketing: Providing recommended guidelines and evaluating current practices. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 1-22.
- Huma, S., Muslim, S., & Ahmed, W. (2024). Understanding the role of organizational intellectual capital on developing absorptive capacity to strategize innovation ambidexterity. *Review of International Business and Strategy*, 34(3), 433-453.
- Hwang, B.-N., Lai, Y.-P., & Wang, C. (2023). Open innovation and organizational ambidexterity. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 26(3), 862-884.
- Jiang, Y., Guo, Y., He, X., & Chen, X. (2025). Exploring the complex interplay of intellectual capital and environmental uncertainty in ambidextrous innovation: evidence from China. *International Journal of Manpower*, 46(3), 430-445.
- Jyoti, J., & Choudhary, R. (2024). Exploring ambidextrous human resource management and employee performance through the lens of managers' ambidextrous orientation and individual ambidexterity. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*, 46(7), 1588-1623.
- Kafetzopoulos, P., Psomas, E., & Katou, A. A. (2023). Promoting strategic flexibility and business performance through organizational ambidexterity. *Sustainability*, 15(17), 12997.
- Kaur, K., & Kumar, S. (2024). Resource-based view and SME internationalization: a systematic literature review of resource optimization for global growth. *Management Review Quarterly*, 1-43.
- Kero, C. A., & Bogale, A. T. (2023). A Systematic Review of Resource-Based View and Dynamic Capabilities of Firms and Future Research Avenues. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & Planning*, 18(10).

- Khalequzzaman, M., Wang, S., Zhang, N., & Wang, L. (2025). Integrating HR, intellectual capital, ambidextrous innovation, and environmental regulation for sustainable success in Bangladesh's manufacturing industry. *Systems, 13*(2), 99.
- Khan, I., Ming, J., Ali, M., & Zhang, Z. (2022). Influence of government supports on small and medium enterprises development: Case study of Swat Valley. *Journal of small business management, 60*(6), 1484-1515.
- Kilroy, J., Dundon, T., & Townsend, K. (2023). Embedding reciprocity in human resource management: A social exchange theory of the role of frontline managers. *Human Resource Management Journal, 33*(2), 511-531.
- Lambert, L. S., & Newman, D. A. (2023). Construct development and validation in three practical steps: Recommendations for reviewers, editors, and authors. *Organizational Research Methods, 26*(4), 574-607.
- Lawler, E. J., & Yoon, J. (1998). Network structure and emotion in exchange relations. *American sociological review, 871-894*.
- Lee, C.-C., Yeh, W.-C., Yu, Z., & Luo, Y.-C. (2023). Knowledge sharing and innovation performance: a case study on the impact of organizational culture, structural capital, human resource management practices, and relational capital of real estate agents. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, 10*(1), 1-16.
- Lewis, W. A. (1954). Economic development with unlimited supplies of labour.
- Lopez-Zapata, E., & Ramírez-Gómez, A. D. J. (2023). Intellectual capital, organizational culture and ambidexterity in Colombian firms. *Journal of Intellectual Capital, 24*(2), 375-398.
- Mahmood, T., Ali, L., Imran, M., Saleem, K., & Taous, M. (2025). *Unlocking the Black Box: In what way Intellectual Capital Enhances Performance through Managerial Ambidexterity and Ambidextrous Leadership*. Paper presented at the Anales Cervantinos.
- Mahmood, T., & Mubarik, M. S. (2020). Balancing innovation and exploitation in the fourth industrial revolution: Role of intellectual capital and technology absorptive capacity. *Technological forecasting and social change, 160*, 120248.
- Mandil, A. D. A., Salih, M. M., & Muhsen, Y. R. (2024). Opinion weight criteria method (OWCM): a new method for weighting criteria with zero inconsistency. *IEEE Access, 12*, 5605-5616.
- Martínez-Falcó, J., Marco-Lajara, B., Zaragoza-Sáez, P., & Sánchez-García, E. (2024). The effect of organizational ambidexterity on sustainable performance: A structural equation analysis applied to the Spanish wine industry. *Agribusiness, 40*(4), 773-803.
- MATACHE, I. C. (2023). Human Capital Theory—One Way of Explaining Higher Education Massification. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law*(29), 363-371.
- Melly, P. T., & Mosong, S. M. (2024). Relating Intellectual Capital and Performance via Organizational Ambidexterity: Evidence from Health Facilities in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya.
- Mohammad Shafiee, M., Warkentin, M., & Motamed, S. (2024). Do human capital and relational capital influence knowledge-intensive firm competitiveness? The roles of export orientation and marketing knowledge capability. *Journal of Knowledge Management, 28*(1), 138-160.
- Mubarik, M. S., Chandran, V., & Devadason, E. S. (2018). Measuring human capital in small and medium manufacturing enterprises: what matters? *Social indicators research, 137*(2), 605-623.

- Mubarik, M. S., Govindaraju, C., & Devadason, E. S. (2016). Human capital development for SMEs in Pakistan: is the “one-size-fits-all” policy adequate? *International Journal of Social Economics*, 43(8), 804-822.
- Mukaro, C. T., Deka, A., & Rukani, S. (2023). The influence of intellectual capital on organizational performance. *Future business journal*, 9(1), 31.
- Mulyana, R., Rusu, L., & Perjons, E. (2024). Key Ambidextrous It Governance Mechanisms Influence On Digital Transformation And Organizational Performance In Indonesian Banking And Insurance.
- Nurseha, B. P., Afif, M. N., & Anwar, S. (2024). The effect of human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency, relational capital efficiency, capital employed efficiency & rate of growth of intellectual capital on financial performance. *The Accounting Journal of Binaniaga*, 9(01), 51-64.
- Odhano, Q. A., Mahmood, T., Naqvi, S. R., & Ahmed, M. (2025). From Knowledge to Growth: How Intellectual Capital Drives Technological Innovation and Firm Performance in Pakistan's Manufacturing Sector. *Annual Methodological Archive Research Review*, 3(6), 147-162.
- Ortiz-Regalado, O., & Guevara, R. (2024). Intellectual capital and financial performance in small manufacturing companies: the moderating effect of managerial ambidexterity. *IEEE Access*, 12, 75520-75531.
- Pak, J., Heidarian Ghaleh, H., & Mehralian, G. (2023). How does human resource management balance exploration and exploitation? The differential effects of intellectual capital-enhancing HR practices on ambidexterity and firm innovation. *Human Resource Management*, 62(6), 933-952.
- Pant, P., Dutta, S., & Sarmah, S. (2024). Supply chain relational capital and firm performance: an empirical enquiry from India. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 19(1), 76-105.
- Paoloni, P., De Andreis, F., & Papa, A. (2024). Relational capital and immigrant entrepreneurship in Italy. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 20(4), 2703-2727.
- Pertheban, T. R., Thurasamy, R., Marimuthu, A., Venkatachalam, K. R., Annamalah, S., Paraman, P., & Hoo, W. C. (2023). The impact of proactive resilience strategies on organizational performance: Role of ambidextrous and dynamic capabilities of SMEs in manufacturing sector. *Sustainability*, 15(16), 12665.
- Rafid, M. (2023). Relationship analysis and concept of human capital theory and education. *EDUCATUM: Scientific Journal of Education*, 1(1), 26-31.
- Rafik, S. (2023). Moving to ambidextrous organization: a systematic literature review. *Вестник Санкт-Петербургского университета. Менеджмент*, 22(2), 191-225.
- Rahma, A. M., Nurcahyono, N., Sinarasri, A., & Ifada, L. M. (2023). *Moderating Effects of Institutional Ownership on the Relation Between Capital Structure and Firm Performance*. Paper presented at the International Conference on Business, Accounting, Banking, and Economics (ICBABE 2022).
- Rajput, N., Das, G., Shivam, K., Nayak, C. K., Gaurav, K., & Nagpal, P. (2023). An inclusive systematic investigation of human resource management practice in harnessing human capital. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 80, 3686-3690.
- Reagans, R., & Zuckerman, E. W. (2001). Networks, diversity, and productivity: The social capital of corporate R&D teams. *Organization science*, 12(4), 502-517.
- Rehman, S. U., Ashfaq, K., Bresciani, S., Giacosa, E., & Mueller, J. (2023). Nexus among intellectual capital, interorganizational learning, industrial Internet of things technology

- and innovation performance: a resource-based perspective. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 24(2), 509-534.
- Rehman, S. U., Elrehail, H., Nair, K., Bhatti, A., & Taamneh, A. M. (2023). MCS package and entrepreneurial competency influence on business performance: the moderating role of business strategy. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 32(1), 1-23.
- Restuputri, D. P., Masudin, I., Septira, A. P., Govindan, K., & Widayat, W. (2024). The role of knowledge management to improve organizational performance through organizational ambidexterity within the uncertainties. *Business Process Management Journal*, 30(7), 2237-2282.
- Rosing, K., & Zacher, H. (2023). Ambidextrous leadership: A review of theoretical developments and empirical evidence. *Handbook of organizational creativity*, 51-70.
- Rulke, D. L., & Galaskiewicz, J. (2000). Distribution of knowledge, group network structure, and group performance. *Management Science*, 46(5), 612-625.
- Saputra, M. H., & Pratomo, L. A. (2023). Optimization of relational capital and the strength of SMEs network collaboration to improve its performance: Evidence from Indonesia. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa*, 16(1), 111-126.
- Sarwar, A., & Mustafa, A. (2024). Analysing the impact of green intellectual capital on environmental performance: the mediating role of green training and development. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 36(11), 3357-3370.
- Sellbom, M., & Goretzko, D. (2023). Introduction to exploratory factor analysis: an applied approach. In *The Cambridge handbook of research methods and statistics for the social and behavioral sciences* (pp. 513-534): Cambridge University Press.
- Serenko, A. (2024). The human capital management perspective on quiet quitting: recommendations for employees, managers, and national policymakers. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 28(1), 27-43.
- Serra, L., Alves, J. M., & Pinheiro, G. (2025). Development and validation of a scale to measure students' feelings about school: An exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis approach. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 10(2), 190-206.
- Shehzad, M. U., Zhang, J., Dost, M., Ahmad, M. S., & Alam, S. (2023). Linking green intellectual capital, ambidextrous green innovation and firms green performance: evidence from Pakistani manufacturing firms. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 24(4), 974-1001.
- Siddiqui, F., Anwer, N., John, A., & Rabie, M. O. (2024). The Role of Human Capital in Fostering Organizational Ambidexterity: A Study of IT Firms in Pakistan. *Journal of Asian Development Studies*, 13(1), 491-503.
- Simsek, Z. (2009). Organizational ambidexterity: Towards a multilevel understanding. *Journal of management studies*, 46(4), 597-624.
- Stoiber, K., Matzler, K., & Hautz, J. (2023). Ambidextrous structures paving the way for disruptive business models: a conceptual framework. *Review of Managerial Science*, 17(4), 1439-1485.
- Sucena, A., Matos, F., & Nunes, A. (2025). Intellectual capital in construction SMEs. *Procedia Computer Science*, 253, 59-66.
- Sun, X., Rong, N., Sun, M., & Zhu, F. (2023). Combining structural and sequential ambidexterity: A configurational approach using fsQCA. *Management and Organization Review*, 19(4), 803-837.

- Taha, N., Siam, W., Alshurafat, H., & Al Shbail, M. O. (2024). Does organizational ambidexterity mediate the relationship between intellectual capital and financial performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(4), 711-743.
- Tang, X., & Wei, S. (2024). Leading for employees' enterprise system ambidextrous use through contextual ambidexterity: the mediating role of user empowerment and moderating role of leader-member exchange. *Internet Research*, 34(6), 2175-2201.
- Turan, G. B., Özer, Z., & Karman, S. (2023). Turkish validity and reliability study of disease-related fear scale in patients with epilepsy. *Epilepsy & Behavior*, 138, 109053.
- Tushman, M. L., & O'Reilly III, C. A. (1996). Ambidextrous organizations: Managing evolutionary and revolutionary change. *California management review*, 38(4), 8-29.
- Vasilev, V., Stefanova, D., & Popescu, C. (2023). Human capital management and digitalization—From good practices and traditions to sustainable development. In *Digitalization, Sustainable Development, and Industry 5.0* (pp. 41-65): Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Vătămănescu, E.-M., Bratianu, C., Dabija, D.-C., & Popa, S. (2023). Capitalizing online knowledge networks: from individual knowledge acquisition towards organizational achievements. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 27(5), 1366-1389.
- Wang, Y., Hu, W., Park, K.-S., Yuan, Q., & Chen, N. (2023). Examining residents' support for night tourism: An application of the social exchange theory and emotional solidarity. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 28, 100780.
- Ward, M. K., & Meade, A. W. (2023). Dealing with careless responding in survey data: Prevention, identification, and recommended best practices. *Annual review of psychology*, 74(1), 577-596.
- Widaman, K. F., & Helm, J. L. (2023). Exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis.
- Xi, M., Fang, W., Feng, T., & Liu, Y. (2023). Configuring green intellectual capital to achieve ambidextrous environmental strategy: based on resource orchestration theory. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 24(5), 1184-1205.
- Yang, F., Luo, C., & Pan, L. (2024). Do digitalization and intellectual capital drive sustainable open innovation of natural resources sector? Evidence from China. *Resources Policy*, 88, 104345.
- Zahid, Z., Zhang, J., Shahzad, M. A., Junaid, M., & Shrivastava, A. (2024). Green Synergy: Interplay of corporate social responsibility, green intellectual capital, and green ambidextrous innovation for sustainable performance in the industry 4.0 era. *Plos one*, 19(8), e0306349.
- Zhao, L., & Detlor, B. (2023). Towards a contingency model of knowledge sharing: interaction between social capital and social exchange theories. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, 21(1), 197-209.